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The Consolidation of the Pharmaceutical Sector in the Global Economy: Growth, Influence, Deviations, and Marketing

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Abstract

This study investigates how the pharmaceutical sector has become one of the largest and most influential economic sectors of our time. It presents figures and information that support this claim and aims to elucidate the factors that contributed to such a rise. Since Alexander Fleming's discovery of penicillin in 1928, pharmaceutical industries have evolved from small entities - often family-owned and operating locally - to multinational corporations valued at hundreds of billions of dollars with global influence. However, beyond the discovery and diversification of drugs, increased demand, and expansion of production capacity, part of this evolution is underpinned by complex, and in some cases perverse, strategies prioritizing profit maximization over public and individual health. The findings of this study reveal that, over the past two decades, the sector's revenues have quadrupled, reaching \$1.48 trillion in 2022, an amount comparable to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of developed countries such as Spain. The twenty largest companies in the sector have a combined market value of \$3.5 trillion and assets totaling \$1.86 trillion, generating annual revenues of \$820 billion and profits of \$181.6 billion. For context, the assets of these companies alone are comparable to the GDP of all Sub-Saharan African countries. Companies, like Johnson & Johnson, have a market value exceeding the GDP of 184 nations. The study also examines and discusses questionable practices adopted by the pharmaceutical industry, including investing billions in lobbying and election financing, influencing regulatory agencies, financially supporting patient organizations, sponsoring authors of "Clinical Guidelines", manipulating and concealing drug research and tests, and directing massive investments to strengthen ties with prescribers, university hospitals, and academic institutions. Concrete examples of these actions are provided, backed by studies, data surveys, and court decisions, underscoring the alarming consequences of this reality. Lastly, the research analyzes pharmaceutical marketing as a primary sales boost strategy. Despite drugs not being ordinary commodities, susceptible to promotion under the lens of rampant consumption, companies invest billions annually in direct-to-consumer advertising. In the Brazilian context, the pharmaceutical sector stands out as one of the main investors in marketing. In recent years, several companies in the field have ranked among the highest individual advertising spenders. The emergence of digital marketing strategies driven by the internet, advanced algorithms, and social networks, combined with advertising campaigns harmful to public and collective health, underscore a concerning and challenging scenario.

Keywords: Pharmaceutical Industry; Medications; Dynamics; Excesses; Advertising.

What does this study add to the existing literature?

This thesis endeavors to contribute innovative insights to the existing literature through three distinct chapters. The first chapter compiles recent data on the global pharmaceutical sector from a variety of sources, including international institutions and authors from diverse regions. It offers a comprehensive collection of updated figures and information, such as market value, assets, revenues, profits of global pharmaceutical companies, patterns of pharmaceutical consumption, distribution of R&D investments, number of associated companies, and the geopolitical market division. This aggregation, unique to our research as far as we are aware, provides a foundational or comparative reference for future research and discussions.

The second chapter delves into various deviations, excesses, and biases prevalent within pharmaceutical companies. By adding at least one illustrative example for each bias and presenting recent data on convictions and the scale of questionable practices, this chapter enriches and contributes to the interdisciplinary debate prevalent in international literature.

In the third chapter, we present an unprecedented analysis of the Brazilian pharmaceutical sector, positing it as a quintessential example of national marketing dynamics. Through a blend of historical and recent data, we illustrate how pharmaceutical industries lead marketing investments in Brazil, outperforming traditional economic sectors like retail. The chapter highlights aggressive marketing strategies that potentially harm public health and demonstrates their role in boosting profits, as supported by financial data.

Overall, the thesis adopts a systemic approach to demonstrate how the intersection of expanded productive capacity, heightened investment in R&D, and a range of unethical practices - including direct-to-consumer marketing tactics detrimental to public health - contribute to the pharmaceutical sector's emergence as a major force in the global economy.

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Introduction

Nathan Mayer Rothschild (1777 - 1836) was a pivotal figure in one of history's most influential banking dynasties (Britannica, 2023). In the 19th century, his family was regarded as the wealthiest in Europe, with Nathan playing a crucial role in their financial success and becoming one of the era's most affluent individuals. The Rothschild fortune was instrumental in funding monarchs, defeating Napoleon, and facilitating the construction of the Suez Canal. Their estates, lavishly furnished with the finest global commodities, stood as some of Europe's most magnificent and imposing structures. Despite his immense wealth, Nathan could not escape an untimely demise. He passed away in London in July 1836 at 58, following complications from a simple boil removal.

This period also saw the tragic impact of inadequate healthcare, poor living conditions, and a lack of awareness about public health and sanitation, leading to devastating pandemics that decimated populations. A notable instance was the typhus outbreak, a lice-borne disease. Between 1918 and 1922, this epidemic affected around twenty-five million people in Russia alone, causing approximately three million deaths (Patterson, 1993).

Amidst the challenging early 20th century, Alexander Fleming, an English military doctor who served in World War I (1914 - 1918), was profoundly affected by the human suffering in field hospitals (Tan; Tatsumura, 2015). Many soldiers, plagued by infected wounds, fell victim to 'gas gangrene,' a lethal bacterial infection causing skin necrosis.

Following the war, Fleming resumed his work at St. Mary's Hospital in London. In 1928, after a vacation, he returned to find that his unattended bacterial cultures had been infiltrated by mold, creating a bacteria-free zone around it. This observation led to further experimentation and ultimately to the discovery of penicillin, humanity's first antibiotic (Shi, 2023). Awarded the Nobel Prize in 1945 for this groundbreaking discovery (Nobel, 2023), Fleming's work not only transformed medical history but also marked the beginning of a new era characterized by the rapid development and diversification of pharmaceuticals and the expansion of the pharmaceutical industry.

The last century has witnessed a series of scientific and technological revolutions that have profoundly transformed pharmacology. Initially dominated by generic, naturally-sourced drugs and artisanal production methods (Pina et al., 2009), these advancements have spurred the growth of the pharmaceutical industry, enabling the mass production of a diverse array of modern medications. The industry now stands on pillars of large-scale production, advanced

technology, stringent technical and regulatory standards, international reach, and substantial investments in research, production, and marketing, establishing itself as a global powerhouse.

This evolution has seen the pharmaceutical industry become deeply integrated into everyday life, with medicines becoming commonplace in homes worldwide. The industry's main players have evolved from modest, often family-run companies focusing on local or regional markets (ACS, 2005) to colossal multinationals worth hundreds of billions of dollars, operating in every corner of the globe.

Today, the pharmaceutical sector is a major player in the global economy, boasting an annual turnover of \$1.48 trillion, comparable to the GDP of major economies like Spain (Statista, 2023a). The top 20 pharmaceutical companies have a combined value of \$3.5 trillion, with net profits totaling \$181.6 billion in 2022 (Forbes, 2023). The industry is dynamic, with thousands of new companies emerging annually. In the last year alone, there were 784 mergers and acquisitions, amounting to \$126 billion (GlobalData, 2023). High-profile product launches, such as AbbVie's Humira (adalimumab), demonstrate the sector's financial potential, with revenues exceeding \$100 billion during a product's patent life (AbbVie, 2023).

While the development and diversification of medications have significantly enhanced global well-being and life expectancy, the escalating influence of pharmaceutical companies in science, politics, and society, coupled with their profit-maximizing strategies, have raised concerns and prompted investigations across multiple scientific disciplines in recent decades.

Already in the 1970s, the French philosopher and social theorist Michel Foucault conducted an in-depth analysis of the influence of modern science in supporting state efforts to control and manage populations. He focused on the concept of "biopolitics," investigating how public health practices, hygiene, population control, birth regulation, and social welfare policies could be utilized to regulate societal life (Foucault, 2008). His work has remained impactful over the years, and by 2023, Foucault had garnered over 1.3 million academic citations, establishing him as one of the most influential authors globally (Scholar, 2023).

During the same period as Foucault, Austrian philosopher, historian, and social critic Ivan Illich also voiced critical perspectives on various social institutions, including science and the pharmaceutical industry (Illich, 2020). Illich was particularly concerned with society's growing reliance on medications, arguing that this trend was fostering a widespread culture of drug consumption.

Two decades after Foucault and Illich, American sociologist Peter Conrad dedicated his research to the concept of medicalization, previously introduced in the works of Foucault and

Illich (Gaudenzi; Ortega, 2012; Zorzanelli; Cruz, 2018). Conrad, a leading figure in this field, defines medicalization as the sociocultural process by which issues not traditionally seen as medical come to be understood and treated as diseases or disorders (Conrad, 1992).

Conrad highlights the significant role pharmaceutical companies play in this process, emphasizing their interest in broadening the scope of existing diseases or fabricating new ones to expand their markets (Conrad, 2005; 2007). This phenomenon, known as "Disease mongering," has been extensively analyzed (Payer, 1992; Moynihan et al., 2002; Heath, 2006; Mintzes, 2006; Tiefer, 2006; Moynihan; Cassels, 2006; Moynihan; Henry, 2006; González-Moreno et al., 2015).

Accordingly, medicalization now encompasses natural life processes like sexuality, childbirth, aging, menstrual discomfort, and menopause, as well as issues intertwined with cultural or socioeconomic factors, such as mental health disorders, alcoholism, gambling addiction, erectile dysfunction, obesity, and eating disorders (Conrad, 1992; 2005; 2007; 2013).

It's noteworthy that during the extensive period spanning the 18th and 19th centuries, masturbation was stigmatized as a perilous condition. It was erroneously believed to be the cause of various physical and psychological ailments, ranging from conditions like blindness and impotence to severe outcomes such as insanity and even death (Engelhardt, 1974). Similarly, homosexuality was categorized as a mental disorder by the World Health Organization (WHO) until the year 1992 (WHO, 1992). Furthermore, it was not until the 11th Revision of the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-11) by the World Health Organization in 2018 that transsexuality was finally reclassified, no longer being categorized as a mental disorder (WHO, 2022).

The 21st century has seen a significant increase and diversification in the health care and promotion sector, evolving into a complex and dynamic domain. This field now includes a diverse range of entities and practices such as the pharmaceutical industry, medical equipment manufacturers, health professional training institutions, health insurance companies, research bodies, and the scientific publishing industry, as noted by Brazilian researcher Kenneth Camargo Junior (Camargo Junior, 2007). These components collectively constitute what is termed a medical-industrial/financial complex (Mendonça; Camargo Junior, 2012).

Parallel to this diversification and expansion, the range of related research has also broadened. Investigations into medicalization are delving into more specific aspects of the pharmaceutical industry's impact on daily life. This includes research into the medicalization of various societal and personal aspects like shyness (Scott, 2006), education (Petrina, 2006;

Meira, 2012; Lemos, 2014), childbirth (Brubaker; Dillaway, 2009), menopause (Meyer, 2001), insomnia (Moloney *et al.*, 2011; Barbee *et al.*, 2018), beauty (Poli Neto; Caponi, 2007), love (Earp *et al.*, 2014), cognitive enhancement (Coveney *et al.*, 2011), psychological distress (Guarido, 2007), human existence itself (Aguiar, 2004; Galindo *et al.*, 2016; Lemos *et al.*, 2019; Stacciarini *et al.*, 2020), and societal dynamics (Dantas, 2009; Williams *et al.*, 2011).

Concurrently, a segment of researchers is focusing on examining the strategies employed by pharmaceutical companies, particularly how these companies prioritize profit over consumer health. Marcia Angell, a notable figure in this field, is a physician and professor at Harvard University's Department of Global Health and Social Medicine. She also made history as the first woman to be the editor-in-chief of the *New England Journal of Medicine* (Harvard, 2023).

Angell's work highlights that many pharmaceutical companies allocate more resources to marketing than to research and development. She argues that these companies often overstate the efficacy of their products while downplaying potential risks (Angell, 2005). Furthermore, she points out their involvement in unethical practices, including the concealment of side effects, offering bribes to healthcare professionals, and marketing drugs without proper approvals (Angell, 2000; 2005).

Among the researchers critical of the pharmaceutical industry's practices, a team led by Joel Lexchin (University of Toronto, Canada) and Andreas Lundh (Centre for Evidence-Based Medicine, Denmark), collaborating with Lisa Bero and Donald W. Light, conducted extensive studies on the manipulation of drug research and trials by pharmaceutical corporations, along with conflicts of interest in biomedical publications (Lexchin *et al.*, 2003; Lexchin, 2011; Lundh *et al.*, 2017; 2018). Sergio Sismondo, a professor of Philosophy and Sociology at Queen's University (Canada), also addressed this issue. He explored how the pharmaceutical industry influences the unseen aspects of medical literature through "ghost management" in the creation and dissemination of scientific works and results (Sismondo, 2007; 2008; 2009; 2018).

Sociologists Piotr Ozieranski (University of Bath, UK) and Shai Mulinari (University of Lund, Sweden) have investigated the effects of pharmaceutical industry funding on patient organizations (Ozieranski *et al.*, 2019; Mulinari *et al.*, 2020). Concurrently, David Rothman and Susan Chimonas have scrutinized the conflicts of interest that arise from interactions between the pharmaceutical industry and medical professionals, including physicians and students. Their research focuses on the impacts of gifts, meals, drinks, travel, accommodation,

education, entertainment, consultancy fees, and compensation for teaching or speaking roles (Chimonas *et al.*, 2007; Rothman *et al.*, 2009; Chimonas *et al.*, 2017).

In addition to the efforts of academics, researchers, and doctors, the United States Department of Justice has been actively involved, conducting a series of investigations and securing convictions against major global pharmaceutical companies over the past two decades. These efforts have exposed various deviant and irresponsible strategic practices within these corporations (United States, 2009; 2010; 2011; 2012; 2013; 2016; 2020). It is crucial to note two key points in this context. Firstly, the legal ramifications, including convictions and settlements, are confined to the United States, the country initiating these legal actions. However, the issues related to the pharmaceutical products in question have global implications. Secondly, while the settlements are substantial, sometimes exceeding 1 billion dollars, they constitute only a small portion of the profits gained from the sales of the disputed products (elaborated further in Chapter 2). This situation perpetuates the troubling notion that in the pharmaceutical industry, "crime pays".

To contribute to the examination of the growth of the pharmaceutical sector and the impacts of its primary players, this research is structured into three chapters, each addressing distinct themes.

The first chapter offers an updated interpretation of the latest economic data from the global pharmaceutical sector (details in the methodology section). It presents information on market value, assets, revenues, and profits of leading pharmaceutical companies worldwide, discussing the regionalization of consumption and the geopolitical aspect of this economic sector. The chapter also highlights the growth of the pharmaceutical industry in emerging countries, a new frontier for the global market. A complex analysis of investments in research and development (R&D) is conducted, examining the expansion of companies, the number of drugs in development, the main actors involved, and the geopolitical competition. Furthermore, it emphasizes the limitations and challenges inherent to R&D outcomes, such as selectivity and investment neglect.

The second chapter investigates questionable strategies adopted globally by the pharmaceutical sector, including biases, deviations, and excesses. It addresses the allocation of billions in lobbying and electoral financing, and tactics to influence regulatory bodies, oversight entities, patient organizations, and clinical guideline developers. The chapter reveals practices of manipulation, promotion, and concealment in research and drug testing, highlighting how pharmaceutical companies attract doctors and medical students. Concrete examples of these

practices and biases are provided (more details in the methodology section), demonstrating their alarming consequences.

The third chapter focuses on pharmaceutical marketing, particularly in Brazil. It reveals how pharmaceutical companies are major advertising investors, expanding into medicalizing advertising with significant impacts on online platforms, social networks, and other digital channels. The chapter examines how these companies often overlook marketing regulations, prompting critical reflections on their practices and influence on public health. It discusses the implications of these marketing strategies and their consequences for consumers and the health system, offering a comprehensive view of the current scenario.

Methodology

The methodology of this study entailed an extensive collection and analysis of bibliographic references, encompassing scientific articles, books, systematic reviews, and meta-analyses. These references were sourced through various scientific search tools, indexers, and bibliographic databases including Google Scholar, PubMed, Web of Science, Scopus, and SciELO. The search strategy centered around terms and themes pertinent to the research topics, as delineated in the summary.

This compilation of references includes publications in high-impact international journals such as Lancet, Nature, and JAMA, noted for their extensive citations, along with regional and local studies from diverse global locations. Additionally, a select group of investigative reports from newspapers like The New York Times and Washington Post, international news agencies including Reuters, and independent journalism organizations such as KFF Health News, were also integrated into the study.

Following their thematic categorization, the references were subjected to a qualitative assessment. This phase entailed thorough reading and critical analysis of each reference's content, methodology, quality, and relevance. Such scrutiny facilitated the selection of the most pertinent references for the study. It is important to highlight that this process of collection and analysis was not static but rather dynamic, continuously evolving throughout the research and writing phases of the thesis.

To ensure the inclusion of the most current data, the research necessitated an exhaustive search across various platforms and organizations worldwide. A significant amount of data was sourced from Statista, a German company renowned for its data collection and visualization

capabilities. Furthermore, economic reports such as "Health at a Glance 2021" by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2021) were utilized. Sector-specific reports, including "Pharma R&D: annual review 2022" by Pharma Intelligence (Citeline, 2022), and "The Pharmaceutical Industry in Figures" by The European Federation Of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations (EFPIA, 2022), also contributed valuable insights to the study.

In addition to the previously mentioned sources, further data were acquired from a variety of consulting, information, and data analysis firms. These included Daxue Consulting Beijing (DCB, 2022), India Brand Equity Foundation (IBEF, 2023), GlobalData (2023), IQVIA (2023), Parexel (2022), Meio & Mensagem (M&M, 2022), and Kantar Ibope Media (IBOPE, 2023). Additional information was sourced from transparency initiatives like Open Payments (2023) and non-profit organizations such as Open Secrets (2023) and ProPublica (2019). The data collection was further enriched by reports from pharmaceutical companies, accessible through their websites and shareholder communication channels.

To delineate the economic profile of the pharmaceutical industry, with a focus on Market Value, Assets, Revenues, and Profit, this study referred to the "World's Largest Public Companies" report by Forbes (2023). Additionally, the World Bank database (WB, 2023) was instrumental in collecting data on the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of various countries and economic blocs. This approach facilitated a comparative analysis between corporate financial indicators and the broader economic metrics of national economies.

The collection of proceedings from the United States Department of Justice (United States, 2009; 2010; 2011; 2012; 2013; 2016; 2020) was pivotal in accessing information regarding investigations and convictions of major global pharmaceutical industries for malpractices over the past two decades.

For visual illustrations related to the themes discussed in Chapter 3, the Brazilian Digital Newspaper Library of the National Library Foundation¹ (BNDigital, 2023) was utilized. This was supplemented by a variety of sources, including repositories from national television broadcasters, pharmaceutical company websites, social media channels, and various online platforms.

¹ *Hemeroteca Digital Brasileira da Fundação Biblioteca Nacional (BNDigital, 2023).*

CHAPTER 1

The Growth of the Global Pharmaceutical
Sector: Numbers, Scales, and Dynamics

Chapter 1 - The Growth of the Global Pharmaceutical Sector: Numbers, Scales, and Dynamics

Over the past century, the pharmaceutical industry has witnessed remarkable growth, emerging as a pivotal player in the global economy. This expansion stems from groundbreaking scientific discoveries that have deepened our understanding of human physiology, disease mechanisms, and the development of new pharmaceutical compounds. Sociocultural and economic shifts, including increased drug consumption, have further fueled this growth. Factors such as rapid urbanization, industrial growth, higher income levels, improved healthcare access, educational advancements, and an aging population have increased society's reliance on pharmaceuticals.

This chapter delves into the present dynamics of the pharmaceutical sector, focusing on its scale, intricacy, and impact. It will present an analysis of global revenue, the geographical distribution of major companies, market values, profits, and assets, alongside the trends in mergers and acquisitions. The chapter highlights the oligopolistic nature of the industry, dominated primarily by companies in the USA and Europe, and notes the rise of pharmaceutical firms in emerging economies, particularly in Asia and Brazil.

Furthermore, the chapter will explore the regional distribution and concentration of pharmaceutical consumption globally, emphasizing the growing significance of emerging markets. It will discuss the geopolitical ramifications of market share competition in the sector, particularly among the USA, Europe, and China. The chapter will also examine the increasing investments in research and development (R&D) within the pharmaceutical industry, encompassing the range of drugs and companies involved in these endeavors, as well as the constraints and selective nature of the research conducted.

The Global Pharmaceutical Sector Economy

The pharmaceutical industry encompasses a multifaceted array of processes, including research, production, marketing, and regulation. This expansive network contributes to an annual revenue exceeding 1 trillion dollars, covering a diverse range of products. These range from traditional antibiotics, whose compositions have largely remained constant throughout the 20th century, to advanced gene therapies and personalized, high-cost treatments.

In recent decades, this sector has seen consistent and notable growth. Data analysis shows a remarkable increase in global revenues, which nearly quadrupled in just over two

decades. From \$390 billion in 2001, the sector's revenue soared to approximately \$1.48 trillion by 2022, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Growth of Global Pharmaceutical Sector Revenues from 2001 to 2022.

Source: Statista (2023a). Elaborated by the author.

These statistics highlight the pharmaceutical industry as a significant player in the global economy. For context, only thirteen out of 207 countries and territories evaluated by the World Bank in 2023 have a Gross Domestic Product (GDP)² that surpasses the \$1.48 trillion generated globally by the pharmaceutical market.

Despite assertions from many companies about the high risks associated with pharmaceuticals, due to the substantial investments needed for new drug discoveries, various studies (Angell, 2005; Spitz; Wickham, 2012; Prasad; Mailankody, 2017) suggest that it is, in fact, a highly profitable sector. This is in contrast to the often-mentioned narrative of financial 'trials'. Supporting this view, the "World's Largest Public Companies" report by Forbes shows that the top twenty publicly traded pharmaceutical companies globally accrued revenues of \$820.2 billion and net profits of \$181.6 billion in 2022, as detailed in Table 1.

² The Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of a country is the sum of all final goods and services produced within the borders of that country over a certain period, typically a year.

Table 1: Market Value, Assets, Revenues, and Profit of the Top 20 Global Pharmaceutical Companies in 2022³.

Ranking / Name	Country	Values in Billion Dollars (USD)				
		Market Value	Assets	Revenues	Profit	
1	Johnson & Johnson	United States	477.4	182.0	94.9	19.83
2	Roche holding	Switzerland	308.1	101.3	68.7	15.24
3	AbbVie	United States	273.8	146.5	56.2	11.46
4	Pfizer	United States	271.8	181.5	81.5	21.98
5	Eli Lilly	United States	265.5	48.8	28.3	5.58
6	Novo Nordisk	Denmark	252.9	29.7	22.4	7.59
7	Merck & Co.	United States	213.8	105.7	50.4	13.05
8	AstraZeneca	United Kingdom	204.6	105.4	38.7	0.09
9	Novartis	Switzerland	200.7	135.9	51.6	24.14
10	Bristol Myers Squibb	United States	161.0	109.3	46.4	6.99
11	Sanofi	France	136.9	136.7	44.6	7.36
12	Amgen	United States	133.6	61.2	26.0	5.89
13	GlaxoSmithKline	United Kingdom	112.1	107.1	46.9	6.03
14	CSL	Australia	94.7	23.4	10.6	2.36
15	Gilead Sciences	United States	78.2	68.0	27.4	6.22
16	Regeneron Pharmaceuticals	United States	74.7	25.4	16.1	8.08
17	Bayer	Germany	70.1	144.2	52.1	1.18
18	Vertex Pharmaceuticals	United States	68.8	13.4	7.6	2.34
19	Moderna	United States	56.6	24.9	18.4	12.20
20	Takeda Pharmaceutical	Japan	45.3	110.3	31.6	3.99
Total		-	3,500.5	1,860.7	820.2	181.60

Source: Forbes (2023). Elaborated by the author.

The data underscores the vast scale and intricacy of the pharmaceutical sector, highlighting its major players: the pharmaceutical industries. Globally, there is a dominance of a few leading companies, primarily based in the United States and Europe, as the table above demonstrates. These corporations not only possess a considerable market share (Statista, 2022a; Statista, 2023b) but also exert a level of control over the market, despite the presence of numerous smaller competitors.

This oligopolistic nature stems from multiple factors. Firstly, the hefty capital requirement for research, development, manufacturing, and promotion of new pharmaceutical products creates barriers for less capitalized companies to enter the market. Additionally, patents awarded to these companies protect them from competition for extended periods, allowing them to maintain higher prices without fear of losing market share. Another significant factor is the early entry advantage. The initial corporations to venture into the pharmaceutical

³ The complete list of the 44 largest pharmaceutical companies featured in the "World's Largest Public Companies" publication is available in Annex 1.

sector, at a time when it was less regulated, gained from this nascent regulatory environment, leading to substantial profits and swift global expansion (Malerba; Orsenigo, 2015).

Additionally, the pharmaceutical industry is marked by an ongoing series of mergers and acquisitions, contributing to the ever-growing capital and influence of many leading companies. While this consolidation strengthens dominant players, it can have adverse effects on the public. These include a disproportionate escalation in drug prices (Rajkumar, 2020) and potential hindrances to the innovation process (Haucap et al., 2019).

In 2022, the global pharmaceutical sector witnessed a staggering 784 mergers and acquisitions, cumulating to a total value of \$126 billion (GlobalData, 2023). Remarkably, about half of this total was concentrated in just the top ten transactions. Notably, the acquisition of Horizon Therapeutics, a firm specializing in developing and marketing medications for rare diseases, by Amgen, an American pharmaceutical giant ranked 12th worldwide (refer to Table 1), was a standout deal, amounting to \$27.8 billion (Sagonowsky *et al.*, 2023).

Mirroring the dynamics of modern capitalism, several pharmaceutical companies are part of larger conglomerates. These are groups of businesses under a unified control center, operating across various sectors of the economy. Although all entities listed in Table 1 primarily engage in pharmaceutical activities and are categorized as such, many also extend their operations to related fields. A prime example is the American firm Johnson & Johnson. Established in 1886 with an emphasis on pharmaceuticals, the company now identifies itself as "the world's largest and most broadly based healthcare company" (J&J, 2023). It oversees more than 200 subsidiaries, encompassing a wide range of activities from medical devices to personal hygiene products and beyond.

To comprehend the vastness and influence of the pharmaceutical industry, it's crucial to recognize that the cumulative market value of \$3.5 trillion held by the top twenty companies (refer to Table 1) surpasses the annual Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of almost every country globally, with only the United States, China, Japan, and Germany exceeding this figure (World Bank, 2023). Additionally, the sector's \$1.86 trillion in assets is on par with the annual GDP of \$1.91 trillion, the total value of all goods and services produced annually by the forty-eight nations in Sub-Saharan Africa, a region situated south of the Sahara Desert.

Examining these companies individually offers further perspective. Johnson & Johnson, at the forefront with a market capitalization of \$477.4 billion, boasts a market value higher than the GDP of 184 countries. Swiss-based Roche Holding, ranking second with a \$308.1 billion valuation, outstrips the economies of Finland and Portugal. AbbVie, the world's third-largest pharmaceutical company with a market value of \$273.8 billion, surpasses the GDPs of New Zealand, Greece, Hungary, and 162 other countries, as reported in the World Bank's annual 'List of Countries by GDP' (2023).

The Growth of the Pharmaceutical Sector in Emerging Countries

While North American and European companies predominantly occupy the top ranks in the global drug market as previously discussed, a significant emergence of companies from 'pharmerging' countries, particularly in Asia. These companies are increasingly making a mark on the global stage, demonstrating robust competitiveness (Jakovljevic *et al.*, 2021). The extended list of companies, as shown in Table 1, is predominantly composed of Asian firms. This includes nine Chinese pharmaceutical companies, four Japanese (adding to the fifth that ranked within the top 20), three from Hong Kong, and one each from India and Israel.

Table 2: Market Value, Assets, Revenue, and Profit of the Largest Global Pharmaceutical Companies in 2022 (continuation of Table 1).

Ranking / Name	Country	Values in Billion Dollars (USD)				
		Market Value	Assets	Revenues	Profit	
21	Daiichi Sankyo	Japan	43.9	18.8	9.4	0.86
22	Jiangsu Hengrui Medicine	China	32.3	6.0	4.4	0.96
23	Biogen	United States	30.9	23.9	10.4	1.56
24	WuXi Biologics	China	30.2	6.9	1.6	0.53
25	Astellas Pharma	Japan	29.3	20.5	11.8	1.09
26	Sun Pharma Industries	India	29.0	9.3	5.1	0.87
27	Zhangzhou Pientzhuang	China	27.5	2.0	1.2	0.38
28	West Pharmaceutical Services	United States	26.0	3.3	2.8	0.66
29	Chongqing Zhifei Biological	China	25.2	4.7	4.7	1.58
30	UCB	Belgium	22.4	16.2	6.8	1.25
31	Royalty Pharma	United States	18.5	17.5	2.3	0.62
32	Otsuka Holding	Japan	17.9	24.5	13.6	1.14
33	Shionogi	Japan	16.3	9.0	2.7	0.88
34	CSPC Pharmaceutical Group	Hong Kong	12.5	5.5	4.3	0.87
35	Viartis	United States	12.4	54.8	17.9	-1.27
36	Grifols	Spain	11.9	22.0	5.8	0.22
37	Teva Pharmaceutical	Israel	10.6	47.7	15.9	0.42
38	Shanghai Fosun Pharmaceutical	China	10.2	14.6	6.0	0.73
39	Sino Biopharmaceutical	Hong Kong	9.6	8.7	3.8	1.54
40	Sinopharm Group	China	6.8	52.6	80.8	1.20
41	Shanghai Pharmaceuticals	China	6.0	25.6	33.4	0.79
42	Jointown Pharmaceutical Group	China	3.7	13.4	18.8	0.51
43	China Resources Pharmaceutical	Hong Kong	3.2	31.9	30.5	0.48
44	Hubei Biocause Pharmaceutical	China	2.4	39.1	6.5	0.05
Total		-	438.7	478.5	300.5	17.92

Source: Forbes (2023). Elaborated by the author.

The Chinese pharmaceutical industry, as represented by the nine institutions listed in the previous table, has experienced significant expansion over recent decades (Yu, 2019; Xu *et al.*, 2020). This growth is attributed to substantial government support and considerable investments in infrastructure, raw materials, technology, and research and development (R&D) (DCB, 2022). Such expansion is concurrent with the impressive upward trajectory of China's overall economy. World Bank data (WB, 2023) indicates that China's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) has seen a fortyfold increase from 1990 to 2020. This is a stark contrast to the United States, whose economy grew 3.5 times over the same period. This remarkable economic surge has propelled China from being the world's tenth-largest to the second-largest economy, second only to the USA.

The robust performance of the Chinese pharmaceutical sector is fueled by strong domestic demand, underscored by the country's substantial population of 1.46 billion. This population is served by over one million healthcare facilities, including 36,600 hospitals (Huld, 2023). The Chinese population exceeds the combined total of the Americas and the European Union (WB, 2023). Driven by these dynamics, China is now home to approximately 5,000 pharmaceutical industries (Statista, 2022b). While many of these focus on producing low-cost generic drugs, recent regulatory reforms, administrative enhancements, and significant investments in technology and R&D have allowed some Chinese companies to diversify and enhance their product ranges. This progress has not only led to international recognition but also to the development of innovative, high-value drugs (DCB, 2022).

This transformation within China's pharmaceutical landscape is further highlighted by the surge in new drug development, from 95 in 2007 to 3,111 in 2021 (Parexel, 2022). Additionally, China has emerged as the world's largest producer of Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients (APIs), which are critical for creating therapeutic effects and form the foundation of drug manufacturing (Nishino *et al.*, 2022).

India, despite featuring only one company among the world's most valuable pharmaceutical firms, boasts a dynamic and robust sector. The country houses over 3,000 pharmaceutical companies and approximately 10,500 manufacturing units (IBEF, 2023). With a diverse range of over 60,000 brands spanning more than sixty therapeutic categories (Invest India, 2020), India is recognized as the third-largest global producer of pharmaceuticals by volume, though it ranks 14th in terms of market value. This distinction highlights India's predominant role as a major supplier of affordable generic drugs, particularly to low-income

countries. This contribution has earned India the reputation of being the 'pharmacy of the world' (IBEF, 2023).

Beyond the growth of their domestic industries (Dorocki, 2014), many emerging countries have become appealing destinations for pharmaceutical outsourcing (Mohiuddin *et al.*, 2017). This trend is largely driven by the escalating costs associated with production, research, and development in developed nations. Countries like China, India, and Brazil offer several attractive advantages for multinational pharmaceutical companies. These benefits include lower labor costs, a growing number of skilled professionals, burgeoning consumer markets, and proactive government efforts to create favorable political and regulatory environments. Such governmental initiatives include the implementation of tax incentives and the establishment of new regulations that prioritize the protection of intellectual property (Kamiike, 2019).

Regionalization of Expenditures in the Global Pharmaceutical Market

Pharmaceutical consumption has experienced consistent growth in recent years, as evidenced by data from both IMS (2015) and IQVIA (2023). This trend is further supported by statistics from the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), which indicate a significant increase in the consumption of various types of medications among its member countries from 2000 to 2019. Specifically, there was a 65% increase in the use of antihypertensive drugs, a doubling in the use of antidiabetics, and an even more substantial increase in the consumption of antidepressants (OECD, 2021).

Global access to medications has improved, but it remains considerably higher in developed countries. This disparity is evident among OECD members, where *per capita* spending on pharmaceutical products is highest in advanced economies. For instance, it reaches \$1,376 in the United States, \$935 in Germany, and \$811 in Canada. In sharp contrast, developing countries like Mexico and Russia see much lower expenditures, at \$247 and \$303 respectively. This difference is striking when considering geographical proximity; for example, a citizen of the United States spends 5.57 times more on medications than a person in Mexico, their neighboring country (OECD, 2021).

The economic well-being of a nation significantly influences its access to pharmaceuticals, both through direct consumer purchases and via government-supported initiatives and policies. Generally, higher income correlates with increased life expectancy,

leading to a rise in chronic diseases and, consequently, a greater need for medications. Additionally, populations with higher purchasing power tend to have better access to both innovative and expensive drugs, which often remain out of reach for many people in other parts of the world.

Data collected and mapped from the European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations (EFPIA), as shown in Figure 2, reveals that the United States and Canada collectively represent a substantial portion (49.1%) of the global pharmaceutical market. This is followed by Europe, which accounts for 23.3%. Among developing nations, China is prominent, holding 9.4% of the market. However, it's critical to note that China's population is approximately 1.4 billion, an increase of 300 million when compared to the combined population of the United States, Canada, Europe, and Japan.

Figure 2: Regionalization and Concentration of Expenditures in the Global Pharmaceutical Market (2021).

Source: EFPIA (2022). Elaborated by the author.

While the bulk of global pharmaceutical expenditure is centered in developed nations, the growing demand in emerging countries, particularly in Asia and Latin America, is becoming increasingly important (Jakovljevic *et al.*, 2022). This shift is propelled by countries like Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa (collectively known as BRICS), alongside Mexico, Indonesia, South Korea, and Turkey (which make up the MIST group). These nations have large populations and are witnessing notable economic advancements, positioning them as key markets for the expansion of existing pharmaceutical companies and for the rise of new regional

and local industries. According to data from the World Bank (illustrated in Figure 3), these nine emerging countries account for 48% of the world's population and 31% of its GDP.

Figure 3: The Group of Nine Emerging Countries, Encompassing the BRICS and MIST, Accounts for 48% of the World Population and 31% of the Global Economy (GDP)⁴.

Source: WB (2023). Elaborated by the author.

The data underscore the immense potential within emerging countries for the expansion of the global pharmaceutical industry. Over recent decades, these regions have experienced profound social, economic, and cultural shifts, including increased urbanization, rising income levels, and improved education. Such transformations have heightened the focus on health care, including the utilization of prescription drugs (Tannoury; Attieh, 2017). Additionally, the aging population, coupled with shifts in habits and lifestyles, has led to a rise in chronic diseases (Nugent, 2008; Nabel *et al.*, 2009), such as cardiovascular, respiratory, and metabolic disorders. This trend necessitates an increased consumption of medications.

Research and Development (R&D) in the Pharmaceutical Industry

In the current globalized and competitive economic landscape, the rapidity of innovation is crucial for business expansion. With the goal of securing technological dominance in their respective domains, businesses and governments invested nearly \$2.5 trillion in Research and Development (R&D)⁵ in 2022 (Statista, 2022c). Almost half of this investment originated from the United States and China, contributing \$680 billion and \$550 billion respectively.

The pharmaceutical industry, always at the forefront of innovation demands, has consistently been a major contributor to R&D. This inclination intensified during the Covid-19

⁴ Detailed numbers and information are available in Appendix 2.

⁵ "Research and Development (R&D)" is the term used to describe the set of activities that encompasses research, discovery, testing, introduction, and improvement of new products and services.

pandemic. In 2021, pharmaceutical companies worldwide spent around \$238 billion on R&D, marking a 74% surge since 2012 (Statista, 2022d). These investments rank the pharmaceutical industry as the second-highest spender on R&D, following the software technology sector (Statista, 2023c).

The development of a new drug is a complex and expensive endeavor, often taking years and requiring investments that can reach into the millions or billions of dollars (DiMasi et al., 2016). To be made available to patients, a drug must pass through the stages of the "research and development pipeline" (Figure 4), a term encompassing the entire process from discovery and development to testing and approval (FDA, 2018).

This process starts with the pre-clinical phase, involving laboratory and animal studies to determine a compound's safety and effectiveness. It progresses through clinical phases I, II, and III, where the drug is tested on humans to confirm its safety, efficacy, and optimal dosage (FDA, 2018). Following successful tests, the pre-registration and registration phases begin, where data is submitted for review by regulatory bodies. If the findings meet the criteria, the drug is approved for market launch, becoming available for prescription and sale.

From 2001 to 2022, the global pharmaceutical R&D pipeline expanded 3.4 times (see Annex 3). Currently, around 20,000 drugs are in various development stages, as depicted in Figure 4. However, due to the intricacies of this process, most drugs remain in the pre-clinical phase. As development progresses, fewer drugs advance to the later stages.

Figure 4: Number of Drugs in the Global Research and Development (R&D) Pipeline in 2022.

Source: Citeline (2022). Elaborated by the author.

From an economic standpoint, pharmaceutical products that deliver strong sales and substantial returns on investment are labeled as "innovators" by companies. In the pharmaceutical sector, these are often "blockbuster drugs" – highly successful medications that generate billions in revenue for their developers.

In the quest for these lucrative "success pills," an increasing number of firms worldwide are actively investing in and competing within the global new drug pipeline (Figure 5). The period from 2001 to 2022 saw a 4.5-fold increase in the number of pharmaceutical companies engaging in R&D, reaching a total of 5,416 organizations.

Figure 5: Global Growth in the Number of Companies with Drugs in the Pharmaceutical Research and Development Pipeline from 2001 to 2022.

Source: Citeline (2022). Elaborated by the author.

This trend is also reflected in the rankings of the largest pharmaceutical companies and the distribution of global market share. The United States, China, and Europe are particularly competitive in terms of the number of industries involved in the research and development of new drugs. Together, these three regions represent approximately 80% of all companies with drugs currently in development stages (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Regionalization and Concentration of Companies with Drugs in the Pharmaceutical Research and Development Pipeline in 2022.

Source: Citeline (2022). Elaborated by the author.

* Asia: excluding China and Japan.

** America and Africa: excluding the USA and Canada.

While the United States (44%) and Europe (23%) have traditionally held dominant roles in the pharmaceutical sector, particularly in the number of companies involved in drug research and development phases, China has been steadily expanding its presence (Li *et al.*, 2022). The share of Chinese companies in pharmaceutical R&D has shown consistent growth, increasing from 7% in 2019 to 8% in 2020, then to 9% in 2021, and ultimately reaching 12% by 2022.

Limitations of Results from Pharmaceutical Research and Development (R&D)

Despite the growing number of new drug approvals and the prevalent rhetoric of innovation suggesting improvements over existing medications, several global studies (Morgan *et al.*, 2005; Motola *et al.*, 2006; Van Luijn *et al.*, 2010; Light; Lexchin, 2012; Vitry *et al.*, 2013; Naci *et al.*, 2015; Wieseler *et al.*, 2019) have highlighted that most drugs introduced in recent decades do not offer substantial additional benefits compared to those already available. This situation is partly attributed to the lack of a requirement to demonstrate superiority over existing drugs for approval and marketing purposes (Van Luijn *et al.*, 2010).

Furthermore, many of these so-called "new drugs" are in reality (re)formulations or combinations of older drugs. Consequently, when assessing the approvals of "new chemical and biological entities" (Figure 7) - which are pharmaceutical substances that have unique properties compared to molecules already in the market (Branch; Agranat, 2014) - a significant discrepancy becomes apparent in the actual number of launches emerging from the pipeline (Figure 4).

Figure 7: Number of new chemical and biological entities approved from 2002 to 2021.

Source: EFPIA (2022). Elaborated by the author.

In the past two decades, the category labeled "other" has seen a significant increase, surpassing Japan and nearing the levels of the European continent. This surge, as the EFPIA report implies but does not detail, is primarily driven by China. In 2021, China authorized 18 new chemical and biological entities, just one fewer than the total approved in Europe. Meanwhile, the United States retains a considerable lead, having approved 35 new entities during the same timeframe.

A large portion of drugs categorized as "non-innovative" are termed "me-too drugs." These drugs consist of active substances that are structurally similar to an original compound, belong to the same therapeutic class, and serve comparable functions (Aronson; Green, 2020).

Marcia Angell notes the pharmaceutical industry's particular interest in these "me-too" drugs, attributed to their reduced development costs and risks, and the advantage of entering already established markets (Angell, 2005).

This strategy is often employed to produce variations that maintain the commercial viability of drugs nearing the end of their patent protection (Light; Lexchin, 2012), or to compete in lucrative markets already dominated by other companies. Once approved, these drugs are aggressively marketed, a topic that will be explored in Chapters 2 and 3. This places marketing and sales departments on an equal footing with R&D departments in terms of importance for the commercial success and profitability of these drugs.

However, this trend conflicts with the ideal that innovation should bring additional clinical benefits to patients, such as improved efficacy and safety over existing options. Moreover, this approach can pose economic challenges for both public health systems and consumers. When marketed as innovative, these drugs typically carry a significantly higher average cost compared to their existing counterparts (Morgan *et al.*, 2005).

Selectivity and Neglect in Research and Development (R&D) Investments

The pharmaceutical industry, driven by the goal of maximizing financial gains, primarily channels its research and development efforts into areas with the most lucrative potential. This often includes diseases affecting large populations, such as chronic and infectious diseases, and rare or complex conditions like cancer. Despite the smaller patient population for the latter, their severity and the limited availability of alternative treatments justify higher pricing for these drugs.

Moreover, with governments, public healthcare systems, and private health insurance plans frequently funding these expensive medications, pharmaceutical companies' concerns about overpricing are seemingly reduced (Prasad *et al.*, 2017). This leads to substantial increases in treatment costs for individual patients, sometimes amounting to tens of thousands of dollars annually.

A global analysis of the drug development pipeline (Citeline, 2022) shows that a significant portion (39%) of research is devoted to oncology therapies, followed by neurological and infectious diseases. While oncology drugs dominate the pipeline and have seen many approvals in recent years, touted as innovative, several international studies (Fojo *et al.*, 2014; Kim; Prasad, 2015; Cohen, 2017; Davis *et al.*, 2017; Gloy *et al.*, 2023) have highlighted

concerns regarding the often negligible, marginal, or irrelevant benefits and clinical impacts of many of these new drugs.

These concerns raise questions about the possibility of pharmaceutical companies being excessively motivated by commercial interests rather than the clinical benefits of their products (Cohen, 2017). The ease and profitability of getting approval and marketing high-cost drugs with only marginal benefits tend to discourage these companies from investing significantly in the development of genuinely innovative therapies (Fojo *et al.*, 2014; Rajkumar, 2020).

An analysis of the European Medicines Agency's (EMA) approval of new oncology drugs from 2009 to 2013 by Davis *et al.* (2017) revealed that most were marketed without robust evidence of improving patient survival or quality of life. A similar trend is observed in the United States, as reported by Kim and Prasad (2015). Among the 187 studies that underpinned FDA approvals of cancer drugs between 2014 and 2019, two-thirds exhibited some form of limitation (Hilal *et al.*, 2020). This problem is further compounded by the FDA's accelerated approval process (Gyawali *et al.*, 2019), which often relies on single or uncontrolled trials (Hirsch *et al.*, 2013; Gloy *et al.*, 2023), thereby increasing the likelihood of systematic biases (Naci *et al.*, 2019). Chapter 2 will provide more detailed discussion on these biases.

Patients desperate for a cure, physicians influenced by the pharmaceutical industry, and healthcare systems and governments pressured by lobbyists and policymakers with potential conflicts of interest (a topic expanded upon in Chapter 2) often become enmeshed in the approval and funding of high-cost drugs that provide limited clinical benefits. Meanwhile, a variety of diseases, particularly those affecting low-income populations in developing countries, remain overlooked. These conditions, termed 'neglected diseases' (Hotez *et al.*, 2009), or considered 'non-profitable,' have historically lacked research and development investment, continuing to cause a high mortality rate in many regions.

A thorough investigation by Trouiller *et al.* (2002) showed that the probability of having a drug available for central nervous system conditions or cancer was 13 times greater than for a neglected disease. Between 1975 and 1999, of the 1,393 new chemical entities introduced to the market, only 16 were developed for treating tropical diseases and tuberculosis.

In the following decade, the trend persisted. Research by Pedrique *et al.* (2013) indicated that among the 336 new chemical entities approved from 2000 to 2011, merely four were aimed at treating neglected diseases - three for malaria and one for diarrheal diseases. This study also highlighted that only 1.4% of the 148,400 clinical trials registered from September 1999 to December 2011 focused on neglected diseases.

Geopolitics and the Pharmaceutical Sector

The present state of global economic output is primarily concentrated within three dominant powers: the United States, which contributes 24.2%, China with 18.4%, and the European Union at 17.8%. Collectively, these entities account for about 60.4% of the world's annual Gross Domestic Product (GDP), which totals approximately US\$ 96.5 trillion (refer to Annex 5 for details).

Analyzing this concentration of capital necessitates a thorough examination of the state's role in economic development. Historically, state support, manifested through various means such as planning, investment, and regulation, has been pivotal for the economic ascension of nations. This pattern is clearly observed in the development trajectories of the United States and the European Union, both of which have attained leadership in technology, politics, and ideology across numerous domains (Poty; Aguiar, 2021).

China, a relatively newer participant in this global dynamic, has experienced even more direct state intervention, fostering its remarkable economic advancement. From 1990 to 2020, China's economy grew almost 40-fold, in stark contrast to the 3.5-fold growth of the U.S. economy (WB, 2023). According to projections by the World Economic Forum (WEF, 2021), China is on track to surpass the United States as the world's largest economy by 2028.

China's significant economic growth has established it as a key player in international affairs (Visentini, 2011), challenging the dominance of the United States and the European Union in 'global geopolitics'. This term refers to strategies used by powerful nations to influence or dominate less economically and militarily powerful countries. Presently, these three global powers are engaged in ongoing competition across multiple domains, including economic, cultural, and military sectors (Damas, 2021). The ramifications of these geopolitical dynamics are far-reaching, influencing nearly every nation worldwide to varying degrees.

The pharmaceutical industry, a key and dynamic sector of the global economy, mirrors the geopolitical competition among the United States, China, and the European Union. As discussed earlier in the text, these three powers are vying for dominance in various aspects of this sector. This includes control over leading pharmaceutical companies (refer to Tables 1 and 2), a significant portion of the global pharmaceutical market (see Figure 2), and substantial investments in the sector. Additionally, they compete in terms of the number of industries engaging in the research and development of new drugs (illustrated in Figure 6), as well as the

approval of new chemical and biological entities (shown in Figure 7), among other crucial indicators.

The already intense competition within the global pharmaceutical sector escalated further following 2020, marked by the outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic, one of the most significant health crises of the last century. Professor Denis Castilho of the Federal University of Goiás (UFG) described the pandemic as a 'geopolitical virus,' metaphorically imbued with the essence of globalization and spreading along the main channels of the global economy (Castilho, 2020).

This crisis not only strained productive, economic, and social frameworks (Gonçalves; Chaveiro, 2020; Stacciarini *et al.*, 2021, Barreira *et al.*, 2022) but also amplified the competition for influence and power in the global pharmaceutical industry. Pharmaceutical companies became increasingly significant, playing a pivotal role in shaping the geopolitical strategies of their respective countries (Mello-Théry; Théry, 2020; Damas, 2021; Souza; Guimarães, 2021).

China initially faced significant criticism for its handling of Covid-19, particularly as the virus originated there. However, as the pandemic spread globally, China utilized its established pharmaceutical industry, cost-effective labor force, and substantial production capacity to amplify its long-standing strategy of 'health diplomacy' (Fazal, 2020; Chan *et al.*, 2010; Youde, 2010). In a bid to cultivate a positive international image and extend its geopolitical influence, China embarked on a campaign of medical aid, donating millions of face masks, test kits, protective gear, medications, and other resources to various regions worldwide, notably Central Asia, Africa, Latin America, and Eastern Europe (Gauttam *et al.*, 2020). This approach is often referred to as 'soft power', where a country subtly shapes other nations' behaviors and interests through cultural or ideological means (Lee, 2021).

As 2020 ended and 2021 began, several pharmaceutical companies released the first Covid-19 vaccines within short time frames of each other. Prominent firms from the United States (Pfizer and Moderna), Europe (AstraZeneca and BioNTech), and China (Sinovac and Sinopharm) were at the forefront, demonstrating their influence by leading in the production and distribution of a high volume of vaccines (as illustrated in Figure 8). This marked yet another phase in the competition for market share, revenue, and global influence among these major pharmaceutical players.

Figure 8: The five pharmaceutical companies with the highest production of COVID-19 vaccines until August 2021.

Source: GCPMP (2021). Elaborated by the author.

As is traditional in geopolitical conflicts, the race for the discovery and large-scale production of vaccines was permeated by conflicts and narratives about quality and efficacy (Damas, 2021). While Chinese vaccines were considered by many, especially in developed countries, to have reduced efficacy, on the other hand, they were the most produced, reaching over 2 billion units by August 2021 (Figure 8).

As Covid-19 vaccines became available, Chinese laboratories supplied a significant portion to developing countries, particularly in Asia, Africa, and Latin America. This move not only addressed immediate health concerns but also reinforced existing geopolitical and geoeconomic trends, further strengthening China's strategic partnerships in trade, finance, and infrastructure sectors (Senhoras, 2021). Liu *et al.* (2022) noted that while the concept of 'vaccine diplomacy' is not novel, the scale and speed of China's vaccine distribution were unprecedented.

During the pandemic, the geopolitical influence of the United States and its corporations faced constraints. These limitations stemmed from various factors, including the more liberal nature of its market, lesser state involvement compared to China, and internal ideological conflicts. The then-President Donald Trump's denialist stance and his 'America First' policy,

focusing on addressing domestic needs in the run-up to the election, restricted vaccine production mainly to the U.S. and a few allies.

Another challenge highlighted by the pandemic was the heavy reliance of the pharmaceutical industry in the United States and Europe on inputs and production from China and India. This dependency was evident in the manufacturing of the Oxford/AstraZeneca vaccine, developed in the United Kingdom but produced in nine countries, with India and China contributing over two-thirds of its production (GCPPP, 2021).

By mid-2021, at a crucial juncture of the pandemic, China had produced 2.5 times more vaccines than the European Union and 4.6 times more than the United States, as shown in Figure 9. India, following a similar trajectory, had also surpassed the United States in vaccine production.

Figure 9: Vaccine production (COVID-19) by country, until July 2021.

Source: GCPPP (2021). Elaborated by the author.

Girón (2022) posits that the Covid-19 pandemic not only heightened the profitability of the pharmaceutical sector but also intensified the financialization of its industries, further widening the gap between affluent and impoverished nations in terms of access to essential

medicines. This development underscores a prevailing focus on profit generation and a financialized economy, rather than prioritizing an economy geared towards sustaining life.

In the context of unequal vaccine distribution, which highlighted the disparity between developed and underdeveloped countries, both China and India utilized their extensive production capacities to strengthen geopolitical ties, particularly through south-south cooperation (Apolinário-Júnior *et al.*, 2022). While China was at the forefront in terms of the number of doses supplied and global interactions, India endeavored to establish a balance, focusing more regionally within Asia. India's 'Vaccine Maitri' (or 'Vaccine Friendship Initiative') program aimed to enhance relations with neighboring countries and allies (Mol *et al.*, 2021). According to Bharti and Bharti (2021), this initiative represents a significant counterbalance in the strategic competition with China.

The Pharmaceutical Sector in Brazil

In Brazil, the pharmaceutical sector mirrors global trends. Medication consumption has been increasing rapidly, and companies within the sector are robust and active (Stacciarini; Stacciarini, 2022). Brazil ranks as the world's seventh-largest population and its eleventh-largest in terms of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (WB, 2023). This economic strength, coupled with a significant consumer market and a longstanding culture of medication use (Stacciarini *et al.*, 2020), has created an ideal environment for the growth of the national pharmaceutical industry and the expansion of multinational corporations.

In the past decade, Brazil's pharmaceutical sector has shown steady growth. Revenues have multiplied by 3.2 times since 2012, reaching R\$ 106.8 billion in 2022 (Figure 10). The volume of medicine boxes sold has also seen a significant increase, doubling from 2.6 billion in 2012 to 5.3 billion in 2022.

Figure 10: Revenue Growth (in billions of reais) and Volume of Units (boxes) Sold from 2012 to 2022.

Source: Sindusfarma (2023). Elaborated by the author.

Brazilian pharmaceutical companies command a significant market share, surpassing international firms. They account for 58.5% of the revenue and 79.7% of units sold in the country (Sindusfarma, 2023). This dominance is partly attributed to the fact that a majority of the drugs sold in Brazil are either generics (35.4%) or branded and similar drugs (48.7%), in contrast to only 15.9% being reference drugs (see appendix 6).

The preeminence of national pharmaceutical companies stems from a complex evolution that dates back to the 1988 Federal Constitution. This pivotal document declared health as a fundamental right and a critical aspect of the nation's social development, mandating its provision as a state responsibility (Gadelha *et al.*, 2012). In the early 21st century, under a developmentalist policy framework and supported by the newly enacted Generic Drugs Law (Brazil, 1999a), the government implemented a range of strategies to strengthen the national pharmaceutical industry. These strategies, involving various ministries and the National Bank for Economic and Social Development (BNDES) (Capanema, 2006), aimed to counterbalance the influence of foreign corporations in Brazil's pharmaceutical market.

Efforts to bolster domestic drug production included financial incentives for facility modernization and technological innovation, encouragement of research and development (R&D) activities, regulatory framework revisions, and the strategic use of government

procurement (Vargas *et al.*, 2012; 2017). Additionally, the influx of financial capital and the execution of mergers and acquisitions have been instrumental in positioning these companies as key players in Brazil's pharmaceutical sector, particularly in the production of generic and over-the-counter drugs (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2022). Presently, Brazil hosts 341 active pharmaceutical industries, with 246 being domestically owned (72.1%) and 95 of foreign origin (27.9%) (Sindusfarma, 2023).

Reflecting a global oligopolistic trend (Kornis *et al.*, 2014), a few companies in Brazil accumulate a major portion of the sector's revenues. Table 3, based on the "Ranking 1500" publication detailing the financial data of the largest companies in the country, showcases the thirty-three largest pharmaceutical firms operating in Brazil, ranked by net revenue. Collectively, these companies generated R\$ 56.1 billion in 2021. While domestic companies are predominant, traditional multinationals like Sanofi (France), Roche (Switzerland), Novartis (Switzerland), AstraZeneca (United Kingdom), Bristol-Myers (United States), and Braun (Germany) also recorded substantial revenues, totaling R\$ 15.9 billion.

Table 3: Net Revenue of the Top 33 Pharmaceutical Companies in Brazil in 2021.

Name / Ranking		Net Revenue (R\$ Millions)	Name / Ranking		Net Revenue (R\$ Millions)
1	Hypera Pharma	6,050	18	Braun	936
2	Eurofarma	5,386	19	Bionovis	834
3	Sanofi	4,725	20	Germed	798
4	Ems Sigma Pharma	4,518	21	Abbott Diagnosticos	735
5	Ache Laboratorios	4,015	22	Neodent	708
6	Roche	3,847	23	Ofta Vision Health	581
7	Novartis	3,443	24	Geolab	568
8	Uniao Quimica	2,958	25	Zodiac	417
9	Libbs	2,172	26	Cosmed	395
10	Astrazeneca	1,941	27	Lifemed	383
11	Elfa Medicamentos	1,844	28	Lafepe	359
12	Laboratorio Teuto	1,422	29	Hospfar	291
13	Blau	1,341	30	Ucb Biopharma	284
14	Prati - Donaduzzi	1,287	31	Itacel Farmoquimica	279
15	Bristol-Myers	1,095	32	Momenta Farma	264
16	Apsen	1,034	33	Nortec	261
17	Cremer	967	Total		56,138

 Domestically Owned Companies (Brazil)

Source: Ranking 1500 (2022). Elaborated by the author.

Despite the robust domestic pharmaceutical industry in Brazil, its capacity for international competition remains constrained. In 2022, pharmaceutical exports amounted to US\$ 713 million, in sharp contrast to imports, which included pharmaceutical inputs and finished medicines totaling US\$ 7.1 billion - nearly ten times higher. This resulted in a substantial trade deficit for the Brazilian pharmaceutical sector (refer to appendix 7).

Moreover, drug production within the country is somewhat reliant (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2018), heavily dependent on production technology, chemical and pharmaceutical inputs, and on more technologically advanced, higher value-added medicines (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2022). This reliance places Brazil in a position of technological and economic vulnerability, especially concerning global suppliers like China and India (Mitidieri *et al.*, 2015). This vulnerability was starkly highlighted during the Covid-19 pandemic, when the Brazilian pharmaceutical industry grappled with shortages. It was revealed that over 90% of the active pharmaceutical ingredients used in drug manufacturing are imported (Senado, 2021).

Extending beyond manufacturing, Brazil's pharmaceutical sector includes approximately 90,000 private retail outlets, such as pharmacies and drugstores, that sell medicines. There are also 6,800 hospital pharmacies and 10,800 public pharmacies in the country (CFF, 2021). Furthermore, the Brazilian drug trade network encompasses 4,600 distribution companies and 74 importers (CFF, 2021), underscoring the significant role of distribution networks (Castilho, 2014).

These figures rank Brazil among the top countries worldwide in terms of the number of such establishments, even surpassing the United States, despite a population difference favoring the U.S. by over 100 million (Qato *et al.*, 2017). In 2021, the twelve leading companies in drug marketing and distribution in Brazil reported a combined net revenue of R\$ 61.3 billion (see table 4).

Table 4: Net Revenues of the Top Twelve Retail and Distribution Companies of Medicines in Brazil in 2021.

Name	Company's Field of Expertise	Net Revenue (BRL Millions)
RaiaDrogasil	Varejo	22,841
Farmácia Pague Menos	Varejo	7,529
Drogaria São Paulo	Varejo	7,507
Profarma	Distribuição	6,117
Drogarias Pacheco	Varejo	3,763
Panvel Farmácias	Varejo	3,219
Clamed Farmácias	Varejo	2,212
Imifarma	Distribuição	2,002
Drogarias Nissei	Varejo	1,860
Drogaria Araújo	Varejo	1,749
Profarma Specialty	Distribuição	1,422
Solfarma	Distribuição	1,148
Total	-	61,368

Source: Ranking 1500 (2022). Elaborated by the author.

RaiaDrogasil, leading the pharmacy chain sector, reported a net revenue of R\$ 22.8 billion in 2021. This impressive figure not only ranks it at the forefront of Brazilian retail revenue but also places it as the 27th largest company in Brazil by revenue. Such a statistic underscores the profitability of the pharmaceutical industry, both in terms of sales and production. According to its 2023 economic report, RaiaDrogasil operates over 2,500 pharmacies across all Brazilian states and is continually expanding. Furthermore, the company boasts 47.5 million active customers nationwide (RD, 2023).

CHAPTER 2

Influence, Deviations, and Excesses in
the Pharmaceutical Sector

Chapter 2 - Influence, Deviations, and Excesses in the Pharmaceutical Sector

Yuval Noah Harari suggests that human nature is rarely content with current possessions or achievements; instead, success tends to fuel further desires (Harari, 2017). This characteristic is markedly evident in the business realm. Pharmaceutical firms, now pivotal players in the global economy and boasting financial clout surpassing many countries, engage in an unceasing quest for power, wealth, and influence. This pursuit frequently clashes with ethical norms and poses risks to patient welfare and public health.

This chapter delves into the diverse tactics employed by pharmaceutical companies to amplify their profit margins. With annual investments of billions in lobbying and political campaign financing, these corporations wield substantial sway over public health policies, sometimes even contributing to grave situations like the opioid crisis in the United States.

Additionally, the impact of these industries on regulatory agencies will be scrutinized. We will explore how they recruit government officials and dominate advisory panels tasked with approving or retaining medications in the market. Furthermore, the chapter will discuss their influence on patient organizations and in shaping Clinical Guidelines, which are pivotal documents guiding healthcare professionals in treatment decisions.

This section will also investigate the questionable practices of certain companies in the pharmaceutical sector, including manipulation, falsification, promotion, and concealment of drug research and testing, frequently risking patient lives. Additionally, the methods employed by the industry to engage healthcare professionals, particularly prescribers such as doctors, through the provision of 'gifts and financial incentives' will be examined. These incentives vary widely, from modest items like pens, meals, and beverages, to extravagant offerings such as luxury trips and substantial payments for lectures and consulting services.

While aiming for a broad analysis of these concerns on a global level, it's noteworthy that the majority of the data primarily pertains to advanced economies. In these regions, regulatory authorities possess greater power and resources to probe into such practices. However, it's clear that if such behaviors are evident in areas with stringent regulations, the situation in emerging and less developed countries, where organizational systems are less robust, is probably similar, if not more concerning.

Lobbying and Electoral Financing

While not directly participating in patient care, legislators significantly impact the healthcare system. Their decisions shape healthcare funding, service provision, and regulatory frameworks. Additionally, they have a key role in overseeing the research, approval, and market introduction of new medical drugs and devices.

In numerous countries, legislators frequently interact with lobbyists - experts skilled in persuading them towards particular interests. Lobbyists, representing companies, organizations, or other groups, aim to advance their objectives within the political sphere. Their activities often involve orchestrating communication campaigns to influence public opinion or fundraising for political candidates aligned with their interests. Despite being a legal or generally accepted practice in many regions, lobbying faces criticism for potentially allowing disproportionate influence by groups, especially those with significant financial backing.

The United States presents a prominent example of pharmaceutical company lobbying, distinguished by its regulated nature and the availability of analytical data. Unlike many countries, the U.S. legally permits its citizens and organizations to hire professionals to lobby political issues. However, this has evolved into a multi-billion-dollar network of intricate relationships, sparking considerable debate.

An examination of data from OpenSecrets, a leading group in tracking political finances in the U.S., shows that the 'pharmaceutical and health product industry' - which includes drug manufacturers, medical product vendors, and nutritional supplement companies - has significantly escalated its lobbying investments.

Analysis of the longest period for which data is available shows that lobbying expenditure by this sector in the U.S. surged by 436%, increasing from \$69.6 million in 1998 to \$373.7 million in 2022, as depicted in Figure 11. Throughout this duration, the pharmaceutical and health product industries spent a total of \$5.453 billion on lobbying. This positions them at the forefront of the lobbying expenditure leaderboard, outspending the 'insurance industry' - the sector in second place - by 60% (OpenSecrets, 2023).

Figure 11: Growth of annual lobbying investments by pharmaceutical and health product industries in the United States (1998-2022)⁶.

Source: OpenSecrets (2023). Elaborated by the author.

The number of registered lobbyists for the pharmaceutical sector has escalated in line with increased investments, growing from 747 professionals in 1998 to 1,840 in 2022. Notably, 64.35% of these lobbyists are former government employees (OpenSecrets, 2023). This trend exemplifies the 'revolving door' phenomenon, where former regulators, public servants, and even Congress members transition to lobbying roles in private companies, often those they once oversaw.

Beyond lobbying, individuals and organizations also contribute financially to political campaigns. This is a strategy for companies to forge closer ties and amplify their influence, often involving substantial allocations to various elected officials and candidates. While lobbying and campaign contributions share similar objectives and provoke analogous concerns about the democratic process, they differ in execution and are governed by separate regulations and financial classifications in the U.S.

The analysis of data, summarized in Figure 12, shows that over the past three decades, the pharmaceutical and health product industry has donated a total of \$292.5 million to Congressional campaigns. These contributions have increased about 17-fold, from \$3.1 million

⁶ The complete data for each year is available in Appendix 8.

in the 1990 electoral cycle to \$52 million in 2020. Additionally, although data on the Federal Executive are more limited, it indicates that \$51 million was directed to candidates in the last four presidential elections.

Figure 12: Donations from the pharmaceutical and health industry to congressional (and presidential) election campaigns between 1990 and 2020⁷.

Source: OpenSecrets (2023). Elaborated by the author.

A related study by Wouters (2020) revealed that between 1999 and 2018, the pharmaceutical sector's contributions to candidates and state committees were even more substantial, totaling \$877 million. Wouters noted that these financial transfers intensified during years marked by significant debates and referendums on drug pricing and regulation. In the 2020 election cycle, Facher (2021) reported that over 2,467 state legislators, amounting to more than a third of all U.S. state legislators, relied on funding from the pharmaceutical industry for their campaigns.

Moreover, congressional members serving on committees pertinent to pharmaceutical interests typically received larger donations (Knight *et al.*, 2021). Conversely, legislators advocating for reduced drug prices often faced aggressive opposition from these corporations. This included nationwide advertisements conveying misleading messages, such as equating price reductions with socialism, potential drug shortages, and substantial job losses, as well as

⁷ The complete data for each year is available in Appendix 9.

the distribution of deceptive and retaliatory material to their constituents (Torbaty; O’Connell, 2021).

The sustained nature of these practices underscores their economic effectiveness for the involved companies, as evidenced by substantial returns on investment. The compiled data presented in Figure 13 shows a striking financial outcome for the pharmaceutical industry. In 2021 alone, the industry generated over half a trillion dollars from medication sales in the United States. Between 2002 and 2021, there was a remarkable 194.4% growth in drug sales within the country, culminating in a staggering accumulated revenue of \$7.12 trillion.

Figure 13: Total expenditure on medications in the USA from 2002 to 2021.

Source: Statista (2023d). Elaborated by the author.

The pervasive impact of pharmaceutical lobbying and funding extends to one of the United States' most significant public health crises: the opioid epidemic. This epidemic has been responsible for over 630,000 American deaths between 2000 and 2021 (KFF, 2023; NCHS, 2023). A pivotal investigation by The Washington Post, led by Higham and Bernstein (2017),

uncovered how pharmaceutical companies' lobbying weakened the Drug Enforcement Administration's (DEA) capacity to control the opioid trade. The DEA, tasked with combating controlled and illicit substance trafficking, faced significant regulatory hurdles as a result.

Key congressional members, supported by pharmaceutical industry political action committees, spearheaded the enactment of the 'Ensuring Patient Access and Effective Drug Enforcement Act.' This law effectively limited the DEA's ability to act against drug distribution companies supplying potent opioids to unethical healthcare providers, thereby exacerbating the epidemic (Higham; Bernstein, 2017).

During this period, The Washington Post also found that 56 employees from the DEA and the U.S. Department of Justice transitioned to the pharmaceutical industry between 2000 and 2017. Among them was a former DEA Deputy Chief Counsel, instrumental in crafting legislation that ultimately undermined his previous agency's authority. Moreover, several former employees shifted roles to oppose their former colleagues and support pharmaceutical lobbying (Higham; Bernstein, 2017).

In 2022, Joe Rannazzisi, former head of the DEA's pharmaceutical enforcement division, highlighted the enduring influence on the agency. Upon his departure, he spoke of the immense pressure his team faced from well-coordinated campaigns by lobbyists, legislators, executives, and lawyers funded by the pharmaceutical industry (Higham; Horwitz, 2022).

Influence on Regulatory and Oversight Bodies

Drug regulatory agencies play a pivotal role in safeguarding the safety and efficacy of pharmaceutical and health products across the globe. Every region operates its own agency, including the European Medicines Agency (EMA) in the European Union, China's National Medical Products Administration (NMPA), Japan's Pharmaceuticals and Medical Devices Agency (PMDA), the South African Health Products Regulatory Authority (SAHPRA), and the Brazilian Health Regulatory Agency (ANVISA), among others.

Boasting an annual budget exceeding \$3 billion, the Food and Drug Administration (FDA), a federal agency of the U.S. Department of Health tasked with drug approval and oversight, is one of the world's largest regulatory bodies. It exerts significant influence on the international stage (FDA, 2023). The FDA's decisions frequently play a key role in supporting and facilitating the approval or withdrawal of drugs in various countries.

To decide on the market introduction or continuation of a drug, the FDA not only relies on its in-house researchers but also consults "Advisory Committees" comprising external specialists. These committees are composed of doctors, pharmacists, researchers, statisticians, business representatives, consumers, and public members. Their input is expected to be unbiased and primarily directed towards public health interests.

Recent studies and findings have cast doubt on the integrity of some FDA decisions, particularly concerning the pharmaceutical industry's influence. Hayes and Prasad (2018) highlighted that the FDA's "Advisory Committees" are often mired in conflicts of interest, affecting not only pharmaceutical company employees and their consultants but also patient representatives and public members with ties to these firms. The trend of FDA staff transitioning to pharmaceutical companies (Higham; Bernstein, 2017) exacerbates these concerns.

Peter Lurie, a former FDA official involved in experimental medicine access and prescription drug abuse control, undertook a cross-sectional study (Lurie *et al.*, 2006) analyzing agendas and transcripts from all "Drug Advisory Committee" meetings between 2001 and 2004. This study found that 73% of these meetings involved at least one member with a declared conflict of interest.

The most common conflicts were consultancy agreements, contracts/grants, and investments, with 19% of agreements exceeding \$10,000, 23% of contracts/grants over \$100,000, and 30% of investments more than \$25,000. Despite these significant financial interactions, only 1% of advisory committee participants were disqualified due to conflicts of interest (Lurie *et al.*, 2006).

Eight years after Lurie's study, Pham-Kanter (2014) conducted a more extensive investigation into the dynamics of the FDA's advisory committee. This research scrutinized the voting patterns and declared financial interests of 1,300 members across 379 meetings spanning 15 years (1997-2011). It was observed that individuals with financial ties to the companies under review tended to vote more favorably towards these companies' products compared to members without such connections. This finding was further supported by Nejstgaard *et al.* (2020), who conducted a systematic review analyzing 86 clinical guidelines and 629 advisory committee reports, arriving at a similar conclusion.

Given the immense profits pharmaceutical companies can reap from drug approvals, it's not unexpected that they might seek to influence guidelines, councils, and regulatory bodies. This suspicion was underscored by a 2005 New York Times investigation (Harris; Berenson, 2005) into the FDA advisory committee's decision to keep two anti-inflammatory drugs, Bextra

(valdecoxib) and Vioxx (rofecoxib), on the market, despite research (Mukherjee *et al.*, 2001; Graham *et al.*, 2005) indicating heightened cardiovascular risks.

The investigation revealed that about a third of the advisors who favored continuing Bextra and Vioxx (10 out of 32) had financial ties to their manufacturers, Pfizer and Merck, respectively. Nine of these conflicted advisors voted to maintain these drugs, benefitting their sponsors. The New York Times editorialized on the questionable integrity of this vote (NYT, 2005). Facing public scrutiny, the FDA reevaluated its stance, leading to the suspension of Bextra sales by Pfizer and the confirmation of Vioxx's earlier withdrawal.

This incident significantly tarnished the FDA's global reputation, drawing criticism for its initial approval of these drugs and the delayed withdrawal process. It highlighted concerns about the pharmaceutical industry's influence on the regulatory agency. During its five-year market presence, Vioxx was used by over 80 million patients (Topol, 2004), generating annual sales of around \$2.5 billion (Reuters, 2006). Bextra had a similar impact, achieving sales of \$2 billion between 2003 and 2004, before being withdrawn in April 2005 (Pfizer, 2005).

Influence in Patient Organizations

Pharmaceutical companies often provide funding to "Patient Organizations," non-governmental and non-profit groups. These organizations are significant political actors, playing an essential role in increasing awareness of health issues, spreading information, enhancing access to treatments, and advocating for public policies and research in their fields.

While the financial support from pharmaceutical companies is beneficial for these associations, it raises concerns about potential conflicts of interest. This issue has been highlighted in studies conducted across various countries, including the United States (McCoy *et al.*, 2017), Canada (Lexchin *et al.*, 2022), the United Kingdom (Ozieranski *et al.*, 2019), Italy (Colombo *et al.*, 2012), Finland (Hemminki *et al.*, 2010), Sweden (Mulinari *et al.*, 2020), and Australia (Parker *et al.*, 2019). These studies reveal that corporate influence often leads these organizations to prioritize pharmaceutical companies' interests over the collective good.

A study by McCoy *et al.* (2017) investigated 104 patient advocacy organizations in the United States with annual revenues exceeding \$7.5 million. The study, which analyzed tax records, annual reports, and websites, found that 83% of these organizations received funding from the pharmaceutical, medical device, and biotechnology sectors. However, due to a lack of

legal requirements for disclosure (Karas *et al.*, 2019), only one out of the 104 organizations openly stated that it did not accept such funding.

The study further revealed that among the patient organizations disclosing donation amounts, 39% reported receiving at least \$1 million annually from the pharmaceutical, medical device, and biotechnology sectors. Additionally, the same proportion of these organizations had a current or former executive from these industries on their board of directors (McCoy *et al.*, 2017). Interestingly, many of these executives lacked direct experience with the diseases addressed by the organizations. They often received high salaries and were seen as contributing to divisions and distancing critics of the industry (Batt, 2022).

Pharmaceutical companies commonly fund activities that help patient organizations engage with the public. These activities include advocacy, campaigning, awareness initiatives, communication efforts, and political engagement (Ozieranski *et al.*, 2019). The websites of these patient groups frequently feature elements like logos of their pharmaceutical donors, hyperlinks to these companies' websites, and content endorsing their products (Lexchin *et al.*, 2022). Such practices have sparked discussions about the potential advertising bias introduced through these donations.

Patient organizations focusing on conditions with significant commercial potential, such as cancer, endocrine, metabolic, and infectious diseases like HIV, often receive more funding (Ozieranski *et al.*, 2019). For instance, the American pharmaceutical company AbbVie was reported by Kaiser Health News (KHN), a non-profit news service, to have donated \$24.6 million in 2015 to patient associations related to its flagship drug, Humira (adalimumab) (Kopp *et al.*, 2018).

Humira, a high-cost treatment priced at around \$7,000 monthly per patient (Goodrx, 2023), has been a global revenue leader for several years (Abbvie, 2023). Financial data shows that between 2010 and 2022, Humira generated approximately \$196 billion for AbbVie, representing about half of the company's total revenue (refer to Figure 14 in the paper and Appendix 10 for detailed financial information). This sum surpasses the combined Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of countries like Mozambique during the same timeframe (WB, 2023).

Figure 14: The drug Humira (adalimumab) generated \$196.3 billion in revenues (global) for the pharmaceutical company AbbVie during the 2010/22 interval.

Source: AbbVie (2023). Elaborated by the author.

The patient organizations receiving funds from AbbVie did not address the high cost of Humira. Instead, they focused their efforts on discussions about the safety of biosimilars, which are similar to brand-name drugs, and lobbied for state laws that shielded Humira from generic competition (Kopp *et al.*, 2018). Additionally, AbbVie's approach to maintaining its market dominance involved circumventing U.S. legal provisions. The company utilized a range of aggressive tactics, including lawsuits against competitors, boycotts, lucrative deals, and filing an extensive array of 311 patents for Humira (Robbins, 2023). These strategies were instrumental in securing Humira's position as one of the most profitable drugs in the history of the pharmaceutical industry.

This situation underscores how relatively modest investments by pharmaceutical companies in patient organizations can yield substantial returns. The millions of dollars in contributions can effectively be used for investment, influence, and manipulation, leading to billions in revenue for these companies.

Influence in the Development of Clinical Guidelines

The influence of pharmaceutical industries is also evident in "Clinical Guidelines," which are essential documents providing guidance to healthcare professionals in patient care decisions. In their comprehensive analysis covering guidelines published from 1980 to 2019, Tabatabavakili *et al.* (2021) discovered that 45% of 14,700 guideline authors had at least one financial conflict of interest.

This finding echoes long-standing concerns about the close ties between pharmaceutical companies and clinical guideline authors, as previously noted by Choudhry *et al.* (2002), Neuman *et al.* (2011), and Bindslev *et al.* (2013). Clinical guidelines, widely adopted by medical associations globally, significantly influence modern medicine. The endorsement of a particular drug can lead to substantial profits for its manufacturer. However, decisions tainted by conflicts of interest can pose risks to patients worldwide. The impact of these relationships is particularly alarming in high-cost treatment areas like oncology, the medical field focused on cancer diagnosis, treatment, and prevention. A study by Mitchell *et al.* (2016) focusing on cancer treatment guidelines (lung, colon, breast, and prostate) in 2014 found that 108 of 125⁸ authors (86%) had financial ties to pharmaceutical companies. These companies paid the 108 professionals a total of \$30.2 million in that year, highlighting the depth of the industry's influence.

Manipulation, Promotion, and Concealment of Drug Research and Testing

The process of bringing a new drug into the pharmaceutical market is underpinned by robust scientific evidence, internationally endorsed by the academic community. It begins with pre-clinical tests in controlled laboratory settings and animal studies, followed by comprehensive clinical trials with human participants. This detailed, lengthy procedure, replete with thorough documentation and regulatory requirements, is designed to maximize safety for end-users and patients.

Following these stages, trial outcomes are disseminated through scientific publications. These results undergo meta-analyses, employing statistical techniques to synthesize findings from multiple independent studies, and systematic reviews, which consolidate research

⁸ Active in the 'National Comprehensive Cancer Network (NCCN),' a non-profit organization that brings together an alliance of 32 cancer centers in the United States.

pertinent to a particular query. These studies, once published in scientific journals, reach a vast audience of healthcare professionals, thereby validating and promoting the new drug as a reliable and effective medical solution.

Presently, the pharmaceutical industry stands as the predominant sponsor of drug testing worldwide (Lexchin, 2011). Research into the effectiveness of specific pharmaceuticals is usually undertaken by the manufacturing company, or by consultants, scientists, and academic groups financed by the company. While these pharmacological advancements often yield significant health and quality of life benefits, they sometimes also give rise to opaque interactions and conflicts of interest among the industry, researchers, and academic institutions.

A systematic review by Bekelman *et al.* (2003), encompassing 1,140 studies from January 1980 to October 2002, uncovered the extensive nature of financial ties between the pharmaceutical industry, researchers, and academic institutions. These entanglements have been shown to significantly influence the outcomes of biomedical research.

This finding is echoed in a detailed study by Lexchin *et al.* (2003), which reviewed research published from January 1966 to December 2002. This investigation revealed that studies sponsored by the pharmaceutical industry were more likely to report results favorable to the drugs produced by the sponsoring companies, as opposed to studies funded by other sources like governmental agencies.

Subsequent literature, including articles, systematic reviews, and meta-analyses, has further explored this topic. Various works by authors such as Sismondo (2008), Spielmans and Parry (2010), Lexchin (2011), Flacco *et al.* (2015), and Lundh *et al.* (2017) have used differing methodologies to demonstrate the potential biases in research funded by pharmaceutical companies.

The question arises: how can a company influence the outcome of a scientific study? The answer may lie in a series of biases favoring the interests of the funding industries, starting from the planning and execution phases of these studies. Researchers testing new drugs may choose less effective comparators instead of benchmark drugs (Djulbegovic *et al.*, 2000), use inappropriate comparator dosages (Lexchin, 2011), or even employ placebo controls (Lundh *et al.*, 2018). These tactics can obscure the true efficacy and potential side effects of the new drug compared to existing ones, thus artificially enhancing its perceived success. Such practices, however, raise serious ethical concerns regarding the treatment of study participants and the safety of future drug users.

Another bias involves the strategic funding of trials for drugs already deemed likely to succeed (Bekelman *et al.*, 2003). This is often coupled with the selective publication of positive outcomes, overshadowing less favorable results (Bekelman *et al.*, 2003; Lexchin *et al.*, 2003). Industry-preferred findings receive more attention and may be published across multiple

journals, amplifying their influence on perceptions of the drug's efficacy (Melander et al., 2003). Conversely, negative findings are frequently ignored, undisclosed, or unpublished (Lexchin et al., 2003; Spielmans; Parry, 2010), as clinical trials revealing low efficacy or safety risks can lead to substantial financial setbacks for the companies involved.

Flacco et al. (2015) uncovered that biases can infiltrate even randomized clinical trials, which are highly regarded for their reliability and involve randomly assigning subjects to compare the effects of an intervention (medication) with a control group. From a business standpoint, driven by the imperative of economic rationality that underpins large capitalist enterprises, it's conceivable that pharmaceutical companies might resort to biases to expedite the approval and market dominance of drugs with substantial sales and profit potential.

The case of quetiapine, marketed as Seroquel by AstraZeneca for treating schizophrenia, bipolar disorder, and depressive disorder (Seroquel, 2023), serves as a pertinent example. Legal documents have disclosed that, to safeguard the drug's robust sales (once exceeding \$5 billion annually, as shown in Figure 15), the company manipulated research to falsely suggest that Seroquel was more effective in treating schizophrenia than competing drugs, despite its actual inferior efficacy (Spielmans; Parry, 2010). This instance highlights the potential conflicts between commercial interests and scientific integrity in the pharmaceutical industry.

Figure 15: Annual (global) revenue from Seroquel (quetiapine).

Source: AstraZeneca (2023). Elaborated by the author.

Further inquiries into AstraZeneca's practices with Seroquel revealed that the company prioritized its profits over patient safety by not disclosing research linking the drug to weight gain, increased risk of hyperglycemia, and diabetes. AstraZeneca misled healthcare professionals by distributing false promotional materials and instructing sales representatives to assert that no studies connected Seroquel to these adverse effects (Spielmanns; Parry, 2010). These deceptive tactics contributed to quetiapine's commercial triumph, amassing \$36.7 billion in sales from 1999 to 2011 (as indicated in Figure 15), until the expiration of its exclusive marketing patent.

Confronted with multiple allegations and a prolonged legal battle, AstraZeneca settled with the United States Department of Justice in April 2010. The company agreed to a \$520 million settlement over issues related to Seroquel (United States, 2010). In 2010, Seroquel was the fifth highest-selling drug in the United States, priced around \$4 per pill (Wilson, 2010), and had generated \$5.3 billion in sales for AstraZeneca (as shown in Figure 15). As part of the resolution, Seroquel's labeling was revised to include new indications and restrictions, enabling its continued availability in the global pharmaceutical market.

Ghostwriting

In collaboration with drug research manipulation, pharmaceutical industries have played a considerable role in the writing and publication of scientific articles. These articles serve as key communication avenues between researchers and healthcare professionals, encompassing a broad range and significantly impacting medical opinions and the establishment of drug therapies worldwide. According to Danish physician and researcher Peter Christian Gøtzsche, scientific communication is rooted in trust; dependable information is essential for designing experiments or treating patients (Gøtzsche *et al.*, 2009). Nonetheless, this reliability is not always guaranteed in practice.

One tactic for influencing the writing and publication of scientific articles is 'Ghostwriting'. This approach is employed by certain firms, wherein articles on various aspects of a medication or treatment are created by the pharmaceutical companies themselves or by professional writers and writing agencies they hire. Later, scientists, doctors, or academics with minimal or no involvement in the research, analysis, or writing are asked to be the listed authors. The real author is either not mentioned or demoted to a co-author role.

Including 'scientific' names as authors gives these articles a facade of independence and legitimacy, while 'corporate' names are left out to avert connotations of bias, distrust, and manipulation. Once published, these articles may be referenced in the promotional content of pharmaceutical companies and in peer-reviewed medical literature, facilitating their spread and, consequently, enhancing the sales and profits of a specific medication (Sismondo, 2007).

Ghostwriting can assume subtler functions, like the 'promotion' of a new pathology or disorder targeted by the drug in question (Moffatt; Elliott, 2007), effectively setting the stage for its market introduction, or challenging research and publications that are critical of pharmaceuticals and their products (Lexchin, 2011). Evidently, this practice can have harmful effects on patients and public health at large. By swaying medical prescriptions, ghostwritten articles, laden with dubious information and misinformation, hold the potential to misguide healthcare professionals and subject a significant patient population to risks.

In the early 2000s, SmithKline Beecham (now GlaxoSmithKline or GSK) launched the Case Study Publications for Peer Review (CASPPER) program. It targeted physicians who had favorable experiences prescribing their antidepressant Paroxetine (Paxil). CASPPER funded the production of articles through ghostwriters that either endorsed its medication or countered its competitors (McHenry, 2010). Many of these articles were later published in scientific literature as case studies.

A decade later, GSK faced numerous lawsuits associated with Paroxetine, linking it to violent behaviors, including suicides among children and adolescents (United States, 2012). In 2012, GSK agreed to plead guilty and pay \$3 billion to settle charges from the United States Department of Justice, concerning not only Paroxetine but also two other drugs, Wellbutrin and Avandia.

The final sentencing report (United States, 2012) disclosed GSK's involvement in creating, publishing, and disseminating deceptive articles promoting Paroxetine's effectiveness in treating depression in under-18 patients. Although the fine was significant, it was only a small portion of the \$27.9 billion revenue from the sales of the three drugs during the years encompassed by the agreement (Thomas; Schmidt, 2012). This case underscored the profit motive behind perpetuating biases like ghostwriting and why pharmaceutical companies heavily invest in such practices.

In 2008, a multitude of lawsuits involving Merck's drug Rofecoxib brought thousands of confidential documents to light. Public health researcher Joseph S. Ross and his team seized

this opportunity to scrutinize about 20,000 of these documents. Their analysis (Ross *et al.*, 2008), revealed that clinical trials and reviews of Vioxx, Rofecoxib's commercial name, were prepared by Merck's staff. External researchers and academics were then invited to be named as primary authors, often without disclosure of the company's funding.

Since its approval in May 1999, over 80 million patients had used the medication (Topol, 2004). However, following years of studies and reports linking it to increased risks of myocardial infarction and strokes (Mukherjee *et al.*, 2001), Merck withdrew it from the market in September 2004. Eric Topol (2004), a leading figure in global cardiology, criticized Merck for continuously publishing communications and medical articles, authored by its employees and consultants since 2001, which vouched for the cardiovascular safety of Rofecoxib.

Despite growing concerns about the drug's adverse effects, Merck persistently sponsored "continuing medical education" events to downplay cardiovascular safety issues (Topol, 2004). The company also spent over \$100 million annually on direct-to-consumer advertising, prioritizing the revenue from Rofecoxib, which was around \$2.5 billion each year (Reuters, 2006), over potential health risks.

After a protracted legal battle, in 2007, Merck consented to pay \$4.85 billion to settle around 27,000 lawsuits from users or their families, who alleged injuries or deaths due to Vioxx (Berenson, 2007). Additionally, in 2011, Merck settled criminal and civil charges with the United States Department of Justice by paying \$950 million, for promoting the drug for unapproved conditions (United States, 2011).

The instances involving Merck and GlaxoSmithKline are not unique. Moffatt and Elliott (2007) along with McHenry (2010) have chronicled various cases where ghostwriting was linked to controversial medical treatments, manipulated to favor corporate interests. This practice raised alarms, prompting the World Association of Medical Editors (WAME) to voice their concern in 2005. Their statement, "Ghostwriting Initiated by Commercial Companies" (WAME, 2005), underscored the need for "authorship honesty," essential for editors and readers to trust the publications and the integrity of their authors. Despite this call to action, minimal progress has been made since. Ghostwriting continues to be a prevalent issue in global pharmaceutical scientific communication, adversely impacting public and collective health.

"Creating" and Promoting Diseases

Pharmaceutical companies have long faced accusations of 'creating diseases' to sell their drugs, a phenomenon known as 'Disease Mongering' (Payer, 1992; Moynihan *et al.*, 2002; Heath, 2006; Mintzes, 2006; Tiefer, 2006). This involves broadening diagnostic criteria to classify more individuals as needing treatment. Often, medications are marketed for natural or common conditions that may not require drug intervention, emphasizing the profitability of pharmacological solutions.

Tiefer (2006) notes that each condition or life event targeted by disease-mongering tactics has a unique history. An example is evident in the late 1980s and early 1990s, when Pfizer was researching a substance intended to treat angina, a heart-related chest pain. During trials, the compound 'sildenafil' showed limited effectiveness for angina but produced an unexpected side effect: increased erections (Lexchin, 2006). This discovery led to the development of Viagra, one of the most well-known drugs in recent history.

Pfizer, enthused by Viagra's potential for high sales, enlisted former U.S. senator and presidential candidate Robert Dole, who had openly discussed his struggles with erectile dysfunction following prostate cancer surgery, as a spokesperson (McLaren, 2007). The company's successful marketing initially targeted older men or those with diseases affecting sexual performance, but soon expanded to include younger men seeking to enhance sexual performance (Horwitz, 2010).

Renowned baseball player Rafael Palmeiro, then 37 and playing for the Texas Rangers, was among the celebrities hired for promotions. He appeared in commercials (annexes 11 and 12), portraying himself as a Viagra user and linking the drug to the masculinity and virility often associated with baseball (Newman, 2006). In 2002, Pfizer began sponsoring Major League Baseball (MLB), a leading professional sports tournament in the U.S. (Lefton, 2002). By 2005, Pfizer not only renewed this sponsorship but also introduced the 'Major League Baseball Comeback Player of the Year Award Presented by Viagra (sildenafil citrate)' (MLB, 2005).

Additionally, former football player Pelé (Edson Arantes do Nascimento), a three-time World Cup champion, was another prominent spokesperson for Viagra (annex 12). In 2003, Pelé addressed the stigmas around erectile dysfunction and the importance of discussing the condition at the 58th Congress of the Brazilian Society of Cardiology (SBC, 2003).

In his analysis of Pfizer's promotional tactics, Lexchin (2006) observed that while the company aimed to raise public awareness about erectile dysfunction, it largely ignored the condition's emotional and socioeconomic dimensions, emphasizing drug-based treatments.

Pfizer's website 'reports' suggested that over half of men above 40 would experience challenges in achieving or maintaining an erection. Furthermore, the company marketed Viagra as appropriate for even occasional instances of erectile dysfunction, frequently using imagery of young, healthy men in their advertisements (Lexchin, 2006).

Since its introduction, Viagra has recorded remarkable sales, consistently generating over \$1 billion annually from 1999 to 2017, amounting to \$35 billion in total revenues for Pfizer (Statista, 2022e; Pfizer, 2023). The global market for erectile dysfunction medications now stands at \$2.30 billion yearly (GVR, 2022), with numerous competitors introducing similar products or generic versions post the expiration of Viagra's patent.

The significant commercial success of Viagra prompted the pharmaceutical industry to explore a similar market for women, promoting a female sexual condition akin to male erectile dysfunction (Hartley, 2006). During the development of these new drugs, the industry sponsored medical conferences and experts to advocate in the media for the approval of a medication addressing this condition (Horwitz, 2010).

Major companies, including Pfizer and Procter & Gamble (P&G), conducted tests on various compounds but achieved limited success (Tiefer, 2006). Ultimately, after considerable pressure, the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approved two drugs for 'hypoactive sexual desire disorder' in women: flibanserin (Addyi) in 2015 and bremelanotide (Vyleesi) in 2019. However, studies by Segal (2018) and Mintzes *et al.* (2021) revealed controversies surrounding the approval process, citing issues like limited efficacy, divergent opinions among reviewers, intense lobbying and PR campaigns by pharmaceutical companies, and conflicting testimonies from patients and experts (Mintzes *et al.*, 2021).

Moynihan and Cassels (2006) and Lane (2008) suggest that shyness was pathologized as social phobia (or social anxiety), a shift largely driven by the pharmaceutical industry's profit motives. In 1999, SmithKline Beecham (now GlaxoSmithKline or GSK), upon receiving approval for the antidepressant Paxil (Paroxetine) for social phobia, initiated a substantial marketing campaign. This included direct-to-consumer advertising on TV and in magazines, with an investment running into tens of millions of dollars (Horwitz, 2010).

The campaign's emotionally charged ads, broadcast nationwide, depicted somber individuals alongside dire messages. Social phobia and social anxiety were presented (annex 13) as crippling conditions, affecting millions. Phrases like "over 10 million Americans suffer," "imagine being allergic to people", and promises of a "happy ending" with Paxil use, were designed to resonate with the public (annex 13).

Furthermore, as mentioned under the topic 'Ghostwriting,' GSK sponsored educational programs for doctors and, through ghostwriters, produced articles endorsing Paxil or undermining competitors (McHenry, 2010). However, the company later faced legal challenges (United States, 2012) linking Paxil use to violent behaviors, including suicides, particularly in children and adolescents.

Moynihan *et al.* (2002) provide another notable example, detailing how baldness was rebranded as a serious health concern in Australia. This shift coincided with the late 1990s approval of finasteride (Propecia), a drug developed by Merck. The company's media campaign, supported by studies and institutes it financed, aimed to categorize baldness as a major medical issue. The campaign linked baldness to emotional distress, panic, and even adverse impacts on employment opportunities (Moynihan *et al.*, 2002).

The systematic influence of the pharmaceutical industry in redefining diseases and broadening the pool of individuals eligible for treatment was highlighted in a cross-sectional study by Moynihan *et al.* (2013). This research scrutinized national and international guidelines established between 2000 and 2013 for diagnosing common conditions. The findings revealed that most guidelines suggested changes in definitions, thereby increasing the number of people classified as ill. These panels rarely conducted thorough assessments of the potential harms associated with such expansions. Alarmingly, the study found that in most panels, over half of the members had financial connections to pharmaceutical companies (Moynihan *et al.*, 2013).

In psychiatry, concerns about diagnostic criteria are particularly pronounced. Several authors have criticized the reliance on the 'Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders' (DSM) as the primary tool for psychiatric diagnoses (Frances, 2013; Greenberg, 2013; Lacasse, 2013; Martinhago; Caponi, 2019; Paris, 2020). Key criticisms of the DSM include its extensive number of classifications (Frances, 2013), its failure to consider individual and socioeconomic factors and to value listening as a method for understanding suffering (Dunker, 2014), and its low diagnostic thresholds, which lead to a higher number of individuals being potentially classified with various mental disorders (Araújo; Lotufo Neto, 2014), among other issues.

The DSM, published by the American Psychiatric Association (APA), is a pivotal manual containing descriptions, symptoms, and criteria for diagnosing mental disorders. In the six decades from its first edition in 1952 to the fifth edition in 2013, the number of mental disorders listed in the DSM has significantly increased, from 106 in the DSM-1 to over 300 in the DSM-5 (APA, 2023).

Freitas and Amarante (2017) refer to the DSM as the 'bible of contemporary psychiatry,' acknowledging its global impact. However, they highlight that its successive editions are shaped by complex political disputes and varying interests. These include pharmaceutical industry influences, patient advocacy groups, health insurance companies, social movements, among others, indicating that the DSM's development and revision processes are subject to various economic, political, historical, and social factors (Freitas; Amarante, 2017).

Among the DSM's most outspoken critics is American psychiatrist Allen Frances, a key figure in psychiatry and former chair of the DSM-4 task force. In a self-reflective critique, Frances has published works highlighting the limitations of the DSM diagnostic system and the pharmaceutical industry's role in expanding diagnoses, potentially redefining everyday issues and normal life aspects as mental disorders and promoting psychiatric medication use (Frances, 2013).

A revealing study by Cosgrove *et al.* (2006) found that 56% of the 170 DSM-4 update working group members had financial relationships with the pharmaceutical industry, spanning research, consultancies, and paid lectures. In some committees, like those for 'Mood Disorders' and 'Schizophrenia and Other Psychotic Disorders', every member had conflicts of interest.

This trend was further confirmed in a subsequent study by Cosgrove and Krimsky (2012) during the DSM-5 development. They discovered that in three-quarters of the working groups, a majority of members had financial ties to the pharmaceutical industry. The committees where pharmacological treatment was a primary intervention had the highest rates of such conflicts (Cosgrove; Krimsky, 2012). These findings underscore deep-seated concerns about the pharmaceutical industry's impact on disease definition and proliferation.

Financing and Gifting Healthcare Professionals

The pharmaceutical industry maintains a close relationship with healthcare professionals, especially prescribers like doctors, who play a crucial role in increasing medication sales and, consequently, profits for the company and its stakeholders. A notable tactic to influence these professionals is the offering of 'gifts' in various forms, a practice extensively documented in international literature and historically widespread (Orlowski; Wateska, 1992; Wazana, 2000; Yeh *et al.*, 2016; Fresques, 2019). The extent of this practice varies by country, influenced by local laws, medical regulations, and inspections, as seen in

studies from Nigeria (Fadare *et al.*, 2018), Ethiopia (Hailu *et al.*, 2021), Egypt (Kamal *et al.*, 2015), Saudi Arabia (Bahammam *et al.*, 2020), Lebanon (Khazzaka, 2019), Yemen (Al-Areefi *et al.*, 2013), Jordan (Alshurideh *et al.*, 2018), and India (Waheed *et al.*, 2011).

In an effort to promote transparency, the United States implemented the 'Open Payments' program. This initiative is tasked with collecting, monitoring, and publicly reporting payments, financial incentives, or gifts from pharmaceutical and medical device manufacturers to healthcare professionals. Analysis of this program's data (see table 5) reveals that between 2015 and 2021, companies transferred \$15.5 billion to U.S. doctors. Of this, \$14.78 billion was categorized as 'General' payments, encompassing gifts, food and beverages, travel and lodging, education, entertainment, consulting fees, and compensation for roles like lecturers or speakers. The remaining \$757 million pertained to transfers linked to scientific research conducted by these professionals.

Table 5: Payment from 'drug and device companies' to physicians in the United States (2015 - 2021).

Year / Type of Payment	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	Total	USD Million
General	2,110	2,170	2,190	2,260	2,410	1,610	2,030	14,780	
Research	148	152	112	104	96	79	66	757	
Total	2,258	2,322	2,302	2,364	2,506	1,689	2,096	15,537	

Source: Open Payments (2023). Elaborated by the author.

Upon analyzing over 56 million payments made to healthcare professionals by certain companies between 2014 and 2018, Ornstein *et al.* (2019) found more than 2,500 doctors who received at least half a million dollars each, with 700 exceeding \$1 million. The anticoagulant Xarelto (rivaroxaban) was the focus of the largest investments, totaling approximately \$123.2 million paid to professionals during this period (Ornstein *et al.*, 2019). In March 2019, Bayer and Johnson & Johnson, the pharmaceutical companies behind Xarelto, agreed to a \$775 million settlement for over 25,000 lawsuits. These lawsuits alleged the companies did not adequately inform patients about the risk of potentially fatal bleeding caused by the drug (Thomas, 2019).

ProPublica, an independent, non-profit newsroom focusing on investigative journalism, also examined transfers linked to specific drugs. Their analysis showed that for 46 of the top 50

most prescribed brand-name drugs⁹ within Medicare, the U.S. government-managed health insurance system, doctors who received financial rewards from pharmaceutical companies prescribed more than their peers who did not receive any (Fresques, 2019). For instance, with Restasis, a drug for chronic dry eye, doctors who received payments prescribed it 141% more frequently than others (Fresques, 2019).

Corroborating these findings, Yeh *et al.* (2016) discovered that doctors receiving financial rewards from pharmaceutical companies tended to prescribe more brand-name drugs over generics compared to their counterparts who didn't receive such benefits. Additionally, there was a progressive increase in the prescription rates of these drugs corresponding with larger financial transfers received by the doctors.

From Large to Small Gifts

In recent decades, numerous medical associations, academic institutions, and varied organizations have highlighted the necessity for reform in the relationship between pharmaceutical companies and prescribers (Moynihan, 2003b). Conversely, a faction of other entities and professionals within the field appears less inclined to critique or scrutinize these interactions (Brennan *et al.*, 2006), particularly concerning minor gifts.

In the routine experiences of doctors and the wider society, grand gestures like substantial financial incentives, significant awards, and large rewards are readily identified as blatant attempts to influence and negotiate. In contrast, smaller 'courtesies' often go unnoticed in this regard. The perception of obligation created by accepting an imported car from a pharmaceutical company at the year's end is far greater than that formed by accepting minor tokens such as a meal voucher at the hospital cafeteria, attendance at professional conferences, new books, custom pens, or an array of pills meant for free distribution.

To demystify this difference, it's crucial to acknowledge that the practice of gifting, even on a modest scale, has traditionally served as a vital strategy in negotiations, contributing to the development of a cooperative and trustful milieu, as Katz *et al.* (2003) have observed. This phenomenon is attributable to the human tendency to be influenced by acts of solidarity, with reciprocity being a broadly endorsed social norm. Additionally, humans often struggle to

⁹ For which drug manufacturers made payments to doctors in 2016.

eschew biases related to personal interests. Our decision-making processes are prone to an unconscious and unintentional self-serving bias. Dana and Loewenstein (2003) note that even when individuals are prompted to act objectively, maintaining impartiality remains a challenge.

When examining the pharmaceutical industry's gift-giving to doctors through the lens of social theories, Dana and Loewenstein (2003) note that these professionals tend to perceive the influence of gifts as more problematic for other professions than for their own. Additionally, patients often believe that doctors overseeing the care of others are more susceptible to bias than their personal physicians. This underscores the concept that it's easier to recognize the bias of influence in others than in oneself.

Among the various incentives provided to prescribers, the offering of meals is particularly noteworthy. Biologically, food is a fundamental element of survival, making it a potent tool for building and strengthening relationships over thousands of years. Recognizing this, pharmaceutical companies have invested significantly (Dejong *et al.*, 2016) in providing numerous meals for doctors globally, aiming to cultivate relationships that could favor their business interests.

The provision of complimentary pizzas and pasta (Moynihan, 2003a) during medical shifts, vouchers for hospital cafeterias, and invitations to upscale restaurants featuring costly beverages (Katz *et al.*, 2003) are strategies employed by pharmaceutical companies to foster closer ties with doctors. These efforts are designed to encourage doctors to pay attention to and value the messages of their sales representatives.

A study by Dejong *et al.* (2016), analyzing 279.6 thousand doctors in the United States from August to December 2015, found that those who received industry-sponsored meals were more likely to prescribe the promoted drugs compared to their peers who did not receive such benefits. This correlation was apparent even with a single meal, averaging around \$20 in value.

Consequently, simple orientation and training are inadequate in eliminating biases stemming from the receipt of gifts and financial incentives. Simultaneously, policies limiting the size of these gifts are also ineffective in completely removing potential biases, even those that are unintentional. Therefore, to uphold impartiality and integrity in medical practices, it becomes essential to prohibit all forms of offerings from the pharmaceutical industry to healthcare professionals.

The Relationship Can Begin Already in University

Business theorists frequently emphasize that for sustained success in the corporate arena, it is insufficient to focus solely on the present; foresight and planning for future developments are essential. Consistent with this notion, the pharmaceutical sector initiates engagement with future prescribers during their university education.

A comprehensive review by Austad *et al.* (2011), analyzing literature from 1971 to 2010 and involving around 10,000 medical students from 76 institutions in different countries, uncovered that pharmaceutical companies start interacting with students early in their academic journey, often from the first semesters. This interaction intensifies over time. Predominant forms of engagement include various gifts, industry-funded educational events, and direct interactions with sales representatives. About 90% of these students reported receiving meals or snacks courtesy of the pharmaceutical industry.

In this engagement strategy, companies frequently target Academic Medical Centers, which encompass medical schools and their associated hospitals (Brennan *et al.*, 2006). The strategy involves offering benefits to leaders, interns, and residents. These perks include funding for research and events, provision of complimentary snacks and lunches, or donations of books and educational materials. Referring back to the 'Open Payments' database, using the same parameters as outlined in Table 5, it is observed that between 2015 and 2021, pharmaceutical and medical device companies collectively 'gifted' U.S. University Hospitals with a substantial sum of \$14.59 billion.

Table 6: Payments from 'drug and device companies' to university hospitals in the United States (2015 - 2021).

Year / Type of Payment	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	Total	USD Million
General	642	758	771	850	1,280	482	395	5,178	
Research	955	1,130	1,270	1,340	1,520	1,600	1,600	9,415	
Total	1,597	1,888	2,041	2,190	2,800	2,082	1,995	14,593	

Source: Open Payments (2023). Elaborated by the author.

At times, the intermediary role in this process is undertaken by non-profit organizations, which are either funded by or act as subsidiaries of major pharmaceutical companies (Blumenthal, 2004). These entities facilitate 'continuing medical education', 'training', and

various forms of interaction. Essentially, they act as conduits for pharmaceutical marketing, subtly disguised as professional education initiatives.

The phenomenon of doctors being targeted early in their careers by pharmaceutical industry representatives, a practice not commonly seen in other professions, is not a coincidence. In a corporate environment where economic growth is a primary goal and profit maximization guides business strategies, investing substantial funds in this persuasive approach is considered an effective tactic for securing returns for investors and shareholders who are keen on expanding their holdings. Consequently, the connections established through this early engagement often endure, subtly influencing decision-making and increasing the new professionals' openness to future interactions with industry representatives.

Intriguingly, the study by Austad *et al.* (2011) revealed that while most students acknowledge the biased nature of industry-provided information, many perceive themselves as immune to such biases. They tend to believe that their peers or practicing doctors are more easily influenced than themselves. This reflects the self-interest and self-serving biases identified by Dana and Loewenstein (2003). Given this context, it's not far-fetched to consider that medical students, with their limited experience, might be even more vulnerable to the pharmaceutical industry's persuasive strategies than practicing doctors, as discussed in previous sections.

University education is a critical period for both academic and ethical development, where students learn to maintain integrity amidst the challenges of the professional world. Being swayed by the questionable interests of the pharmaceutical industry is not conducive to this goal. Moreover, Rogers *et al.* (2004) caution against viewing the acceptance of benefits from pharmaceutical companies as either a form of long-term indebtedness post-graduation or as a 'simple medical privilege' stemming from professional prestige. The former is clearly problematic, but the latter can lead to desensitization to the needs of others, potentially fostering a sense of superiority over peers in other health fields and even patients, thereby inadvertently placing doctors in a higher social class.

Therefore, it's vital for medical institutions, academic centers, educators, and students to consciously distance themselves from direct funding and any potentially harmful influences exerted by the pharmaceutical industry. Moving towards an independent medical education, both in terms of information sources and funding, is essential. Universities, and particularly professors as the primary educators, should play a pivotal role in this restructuring. They must set an example by avoiding questionable relationships, educating and safeguarding students from early on about the tactics and investments made by pharmaceutical companies in their interactions.

CHAPTER 3

Pharmaceutical Marketing: Strategies and
Challenges from the Brazilian Perspective

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In our consumption-driven economy, marketing plays an increasingly vital role in shaping contemporary society. Financially speaking, the justification for a product's design, mass production, authorization for commercialization, and market presence hinges on its ability to persuade the public of its necessity, thereby closing the loop of profit generation.

Within this framework, advertising has emerged as an essential tool for the triumph of major corporations, often initiating even before the production phase (Santos, 2000). A prime illustration of this is the American multinational Amazon, which allocated around \$20 billion to marketing in 2022 (Johnson, 2023). This investment, amounting to \$54.8 million daily, underscores their commitment to reinforcing the global need for their products.

In the pharmaceutical industry, one might expect a different approach since medications aren't typical consumer items to be marketed under standard consumerism practices. Yet, the distinction often blurs. In many countries, including Brazil—the context of this study—the pharmaceutical sector is a prominent marketer. Here, several pharmaceutical companies lead in advertising expenditures.

This chapter aims to dissect the impact of consumer-targeted advertising in the pharmaceutical industry's dynamics. It begins with an overview of the fundamental concepts related to the topic. Then, it delves into the historical evolution of pharmaceutical marketing in Brazil, spotlighting infamous instances of deceptive advertising. These include marketing harmful substances like cocaine as remedies for coughs, pains, and inflammations, and promoting beer as a treatment for anemia and paleness in women and children.

The discussion extends to modern medicine advertising, exploring the diversification and expansion of pharmaceutical marketing. This includes sponsorship in football, reality shows, social media, and more. Driven by algorithms and AI, this sector now incorporates new players such as virtual characters and digital influencers who endorse medications.

The chapter concludes with an examination of Brazilian laws governing pharmaceutical marketing. It underscores their limited efficacy, largely due to inadequate enforcement and the absence of severe penalties deterring companies from legal infringements.

Reflections on the Power and Nature of Marketing

June 14, 2021, marked a notable event when Cristiano Ronaldo, a globally recognized soccer player, visibly moved two Coca-Cola bottles away from him during a press conference. This action coincided with a \$4 billion decline in Coca-Cola's market value on the New York Stock Exchange (Villegas, 2021). Ronaldo's immense social media influence, particularly on Instagram where he boasts around 600 million followers, underscores his impact.

The incident and its subsequent financial ripple effect underscore the significant role of marketing and the power of celebrity influence on consumer behavior. Ronaldo's ability to command up to \$1.6 million for a single promotional Instagram post (Braun, 2021) illustrates this influence. The income from these endorsements often exceeds his already substantial earnings from his soccer career.

Advertising, a key component in the machinery of globalized capitalism, plays a vital role in shaping the production and consumption of goods. This system's dynamics heavily influence consumer behaviors, largely through marketing campaigns. These campaigns transform ordinary products into seemingly unique items, imbued with subjective values. They are designed to evoke a spectrum of emotions, from desire to a sense of empowerment, ultimately driving sales. This emotional engagement distances consumers from the actual use value and need for a specific product or service. Instead, they are drawn to the aspirational pleasures and experiences that these products purportedly offer (Jhally, 2014).

Daniel Kahneman, a Nobel Prize-winning psychologist and economist, has made significant contributions to understanding the psychological mechanisms underlying marketing's influence (Kahneman, 2011). He found that the brain, being averse to mental effort, often equates familiarity with truthfulness, highlighting the effectiveness of marketing's repetitive strategies.

This concept aligns with the "mere exposure effect," initially theorized by Gustav Theodor Fechner, a pioneering figure in experimental psychology, and later expanded upon by social psychologist Robert Zajonc. Zajonc's research in 1968 demonstrated that repeated exposure to stimuli, such as advertisements, fosters a fondness in the human mind. The repeated exposure principle is rooted in evolutionary biology; animals, including humans, have developed to approach unfamiliar stimuli with caution. Repeated exposure replaces this initial apprehension with positive feelings of familiarity and security (Zajonc, 1968).

In addition to repetition, marketing strategies employ everyday language, memorable logos and slogans, musical elements, and strategic color choices. These elements enhance cognitive comfort and reduce tension when encountering new information, such as products, services, or brands. This approach increases the perceived trustworthiness of the advertised material (Kahneman, 2011).

The Nature of Pharmaceutical Marketing: Health Versus Advertising

In the competitive and lucrative realm of pharmaceuticals, as outlined in the first chapter, marketing plays a pivotal role in driving drug sales (Brennan *et al.*, 2009). This sector, however, is marked by a paradox. Unlike typical consumer goods, medications hold a distinct classification (Rabello; Camargo Junior, 2012), creating a tension between the drive for competitiveness and profit, and the commitment to health and collective welfare.

Pharmaceutical companies, often criticized for overshadowing medical care, argue that advertising is crucial for raising awareness about underrecognized health issues and for introducing new pharmacological advancements. These campaigns aim to inform the public about conditions they might be unaware of, or novel scientific breakthroughs. As a result, individuals might perceive themselves as benefiting from these drugs upon purchase, believing in immediate cure (Ebeling, 2011). Moreover, the standard advisory in advertisements—'if symptoms persist, consult a doctor' (Anvisa, 2020)—is presented as a gesture of care towards the audience's wellbeing.

This brings us to a critical question: Can there be a balance between the rational use of medications and the incessant drive for profit growth in the pharmaceutical industry? Or is drug marketing simply another sales-boosting strategy, akin to practices in other sectors?

The financial priorities of leading pharmaceutical companies have been under scrutiny for their hefty advertising budgets, which can account for 25% to 35% of their revenues (Angell, 2005; Lauzon; Hasbani, 2006; Ferreira, 2008). Gagnon and Lexchin (2008) found that in the United States, spending on 'promotion and marketing' is double that of 'research and development' for new drugs or their enhancement.

Pharmaceutical Marketing in Brazil

In the contemporary pharmaceutical industry's business model, allowing direct consumer engagement through advertising is a key strategy to boost profits. In today's fast-paced society, where time is a scarce commodity, the approach of marketing medications directly to households, bypassing the physician as an intermediary, offers significant advantages to these companies.

The practice of drug marketing is not novel nor exclusive to Brazil; it has been well-documented across various regions globally (Mintzes *et al.*, 2003; Delorme *et al.*, 2010; Lee *et*

al., 2015; Applequist; Ball, 2018). In Brazil, the history of medication promotion is extensive, with marketing artifacts dating back to the early 20th century (Bueno; Taitelbaum, 2008). Initially, in the absence of mass media platforms like television and radio, medications were promoted through newspapers, magazines, and posters in public transit systems.

This historical overview situates these advertisements in a period when Brazil was transitioning into a Republic. The nation was experiencing urbanization, with a significant population shift from rural to urban areas. In this era, public health access was sparse, and knowledge of the medical profession was confined to a select few.

As the decades progressed, pharmaceutical advertisements increasingly mirrored the dominant cultural norms and societal values. These ads often portrayed natural aspects, such as "thinness," and certain lifestyles as if they were severe medical conditions requiring treatment with "innovative" and newly launched drugs (as depicted in Figure 16).

Headache remedies were advertised as vital for enhancing the physical and mental vigor of the "modern" individual, thus establishing a connection between pharmaceutical usage and personal and professional achievement. Additionally, women often appeared as "questioning" figures in the advertisements, being encouraged to adopt medications as a "solution" in their routines.

Figure 16: Pharmaceutical advertisements reflecting contemporary sociocultural issues.

Source: BNDigital (2023). Elaborated by the author.

In this period of emerging political, state, and legal structures, Brazil saw the rise of its first national "pharmaceutical industries," alongside an increase in importing pharmacological substances from the global market. However, this era of burgeoning production, commercialization, and profitability was often marked by the sale of purported medications offering unrealistic cures for prevalent diseases like syphilis, which were marketed with therapeutic claims even before the discovery of penicillin (as shown in Figure 17).

The low levels of education, coupled with the near-absence or complicity of state regulation with industrial bourgeoisie interests, facilitated the growth of misleading advertising and medication sales. In this environment, rife with misinformation and lacking medical and governmental oversight, self-medication, often influenced by advertising, became increasingly prevalent. Harmful substances were widely marketed as medicines and prominently featured in advertisements (illustrated in Figure 17). Cocaine and heroin were promoted as treatments for coughs, pains, and inflammations. Sweetened beers were falsely advertised as remedies for anemia and paleness, targeting women and children, while products like condensed milk, high in sugar and low in nutritional value, were touted as ideal substitutes for breast milk.

Figure 17: Advertisements showcasing cocaine lozenges, ineffective drugs, condensed milk, and beer as purportedly modern and effective medications.

Source: BNDigital (2023). Elaborated by the author.

Over time, the tactics used in pharmaceutical advertising to engage Brazilian consumers have evolved markedly. Presently, television and the internet, with their extensive reach and deep societal penetration, have overtaken traditional mediums like posters, pamphlets, radio, and newspapers as the primary channels for medication advertising. Leveraging advancements from the scientific and technological revolution, marketing and advertising methods have become more sophisticated and instrumental in driving sales, contributing to the sustained growth of the pharmaceutical industry's profitability.

Professor Paulo Vaz, a Communication Theory specialist at the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, notes that contemporary advertising still employs persuasive rhetorical strategies (Vaz; Portugal, 2013; Vaz, 2015). Vaz points out that advertisements often deliberately use vague symptom descriptions to allow audiences to personalize their existential problems (Vaz, 2015). Common life experiences such as sadness, occasional anxiety, inattention, fatigue, and difficulties in work or family life are sometimes portrayed as indicators of potential modern illnesses or conditions (Rabello; Camargo Junior, 2012; Vaz, 2015). This approach subtly suggests that anyone could be affected by a particular disease, prompting viewers to perceive themselves as potential patients, thereby creating a demand rooted in subjectivity (Dantas, 2009).

Today, another prevalent tactic in pharmaceutical advertising is its presentation under the guise of information (Fagundes *et al.*, 2007; Ramalho, 2008; Nascimento, 2010). In this approach, advertisements are positioned as crucial sources of health knowledge, purportedly enhancing individual and collective well-being. To lend credibility, commercials often feature "experts" in professional attire, who communicate in simple, easily understandable language for the general audience.

A common format employed in these commercials is the "before and after" narrative (Vaz, 2015). They showcase stark contrasts through images or testimonials: a transition from illness to health, inactive to active lifestyles, or from a state of depression to happiness, in line with the advertised medication's intended effects. These ads aim to alert viewers by starting with the depiction of everyday symptoms and personal accounts. They suggest that these symptoms could signify a specific medical condition, highlighting the availability of treatment, often the product being advertised. The commercial typically concludes with a portrayal of positive outcomes, featuring individuals who appear happier and "healed" due to the medication.

Dimension and Complexity of Pharmaceutical Marketing Today

The presence of the pharmaceutical industry within Brazilian television programming has expanded significantly, not just limited to advertising slots. This includes pharmaceutical companies and retail drugstore chains acting as main or intermittent sponsors, channeling substantial funds to TV hosts and media groups. This strategy allows for the smooth integration of their products and messages into the programming, especially during peak viewing periods. TV hosts and media figures often endorse these products, sharing their own positive experiences, which enhances the visibility and perceived trustworthiness of these medications.

Figure 18: Hosts perform merchandising and recommend pharmaceutical products during their television programs.

Source: Record (2020); SBT (2021). Elaborated by the author.

In 2021, SBT (*Sistema Brasileiro de Televisão*) - a Brazilian free-to-air television network - invested US\$ 6 million (R\$ 31 million) to secure exclusive broadcasting rights for the South American National Teams Football Championship, known as the "Copa America" (Mattos, 2021). This included the much-awaited final between Brazil and Argentina at Maracanã, where pharmaceutical advertisements were prominently featured.

A standout advertisement was broadcast during the half-time break. The channel's lead announcer, capitalizing on the high viewership, engaged in marketing a medication from the Brazilian pharmaceutical company EMS (Figure 19). Linking the product to the ongoing sports

event, the announcer promoted this medication, identified in its leaflet as "a mild sedative and sleep aid for insomnia associated with anxiety" (Sominex, 2023), in a specific manner:

Game Break, Argentina is beating Brazil. It's the Copa America final, 1-0. And everyone gets tense with the national team on the field. If your routine feels like that game where every move makes you anxious, irritated, and in the end, sleepless. You need to know about Sominex! With an exclusive formula, Sominex is a natural sedative for those who suffer from anxiety, irritability, and insomnia. For more peaceful days, full nights of relaxation, SO-MI-NEX [spoken slowly], which is from E-M-S [spoken slowly]. The largest pharmaceutical company in Brazil! For nearly sixty years innovating so that the best medications are in the hands of all Brazilians and of course, in your hands. Whenever you need, count on E-M-S [spoken slowly] medications. EMS thanks all doctors, pharmacists, and consumers for being the most remembered medicine company in Brazil. E-M-S! [spoken slowly]. I'll repeat, E-M-S! [spoken slowly]. Your health deserves it! (SBT, 2021)

Along with the promotion of "Sominex sedative," SBT also broadcast an advertisement for the "Pague Menos" pharmacy chain during the same interval. As the game recommenced, electronic rotating panels around the field showcased ads from "Cimed," a pharmaceutical company, and "Pague Menos" once more. Both entities are official sponsors of the Brazilian national football team (CBF, 2023).

Figure 19: Collection of pharmaceutical sector advertisements aired during the 2021 Copa America final.

Source: SBT (2021). Elaborated by the author.

While the specific investment amount in the aforementioned merchandising has not been revealed, data from Meio & Mensagem (M&M, 2022) - a Brazilian marketing and communication market research firm - shows that in 2020, the pharmaceutical company EMS invested approximately 497 million Brazilian reais in television advertising, making it the ninth largest advertiser in Brazil. On its website, EMS boasts having the "largest portfolio of medications in Brazil", with around five hundred products covering 96% of therapeutic classes and an annual production capacity of 1 billion medication boxes (EMS, 2023).

Cimed has expressed that sponsoring the Brazilian National Football Team has been an ambition since 2016 (Cimed, 2022). Leveraging the popularity of coach Tite before the 2018 World Cup, Cimed initiated an advertising campaign costing 15 million reais, featuring him and decorating 20,000 pharmacies nationwide in green and yellow (annex 14). With 65% of its production focused on "Over the Counter (OTCs)" products - medications available without prescription - Cimed's advertising efforts are key to driving sales (Cimed, 2022).

Beyond football, Cimed's sponsorship extends to other sports. This includes the Brazilian Volleyball Confederation (CBV), the Brazilian Basketball Confederation (CBB), and motorsport (Figure 20), resulting in backing 15 drivers across eight categories. In 2021, aligning with a shift in marketing strategy, Cimed started sponsoring "Real E-Sports" in the "Brazilian League of Free Fire", a highly popular electronic game (Cimed, 2022).

Figure 20: Multiple sponsorships of the Brazilian pharmaceutical company Cimed.

Fonte: Cimed (2022). Elaborated by the author.

The substantial investment in marketing seems to be paying off for the pharmaceutical company. Cimed reports a sales growth rate that is threefold the national average in its sector, positioning itself as the market leader in OTC (Over the Counter) sales in Brazil (Cimed, 2022). The company also notes an annual growth rate of about 25% from 2018 to 2020, culminating in an annual gross revenue exceeding R\$ 2 billion and a net profit of R\$ 320 million (Cimed, 2022). Additionally, Cimed has plans to introduce 50 new generic medications to the national market in the near future.

Pharmaceutical advertising, though seemingly straightforward and sincere, involves considerable research, investment, and technique in its creation. Take, for instance, the campaign for "Next," a medication for flu and cold symptoms. This campaign was developed through an intricate regional stratification strategy, utilizing a behavioral study by IQVIA, a North American healthcare research multinational, and insights from the Brazilian meteorological service "Climatempo". This research aimed to understand how people in different regions of Brazil respond to the flu and how weather patterns influence regional viral occurrences throughout the year (Genomma, 2022).

In response to these findings, in April 2020, a series of commercials was released on Brazilian television. To maximize its impact, the campaign included a national version and sixteen regional variants (Genomma, 2022). The national version featured a news anchor from each Brazilian region (Figure 21), while the regional versions starred local news presenters. This tactic was employed to enhance cultural and regional relatability, with each version addressing specific local issues that contribute to flu outbreaks and connecting them to the necessity of using the advertised medication.

Main presenter: Here in the Southeast, it's cold, rain, heat, all in the same day. That's when the flu gets you! [Voice pronounces the medication name: NEXT!]. *Presenter 2:* In the Northeast, with this heat, you can't escape the air conditioning, and it's this temperature change that the flu likes! [NEXT!]. *Presenter 3:* Here in the South, a hot shower and wet hair mean flu [NEXT!]. *Presenter 4:* In the Midwest, we already know, the climate is dry and the weather changes a lot, so when immunity drops, the flu strikes immediately! [NEXT!]. *Presenter 5:* In the North, the rain catches us by surprise, and when clothes get wet, it's certain flu! [NEXT!]. *Main presenter:* When the flu comes, I say NEXT! Next has a combination of three potent active ingredients. Paracetamol treats pain and fever. Chlorpheniramine for anti-allergic action and Phenylephrine as a nasal decongestant. Against flu and colds, say NEXT! (Record, 2020).

Figure 21: National circulation version of the "Next" cold medicine television advertisement.

Source: Record (2020) e Genomma (2022). Elaborated by the author.

Financing such a multifaceted production, encompassing research, marketing expertise, journalists, recording studios, editing, broadcasting across national and regional affiliate stations, and more, demands a substantial capital investment. In line with this, "Genomma Lab", a Mexican pharmaceutical laboratory and the proprietor of the Next medication, committed over R\$ 1 billion to television advertising in Brazil for the year 2020, coinciding with the airing of the commercial (M&M, 2022). This expenditure positioned Genomma Lab as the second-highest spender in advertising for that year.

Hypera Pharma, a Brazilian conglomerate encompassing various laboratories, brands, and ventures in the pharmaceutical sector, is another instance of significant capital allocation towards marketing. Between 2017 and 2020, the company invested over R\$ 3.2 billion in television advertising in Brazil (M&M, 2022).

Seeking visibility through Brazil's immensely popular football, in September 2020, Hypera Pharma acquired naming rights for the Arena Corinthians, the stadium of the country's second-largest football fan base. The stadium was renamed "Neo Química Arena", after one of the conglomerate's laboratories (NQA, 2022). This deal, involving an investment of 300 million reais, will span twenty years, the duration of the naming rights (Laier, 2020).

Further solidifying their association with football, in May 2021, Neo Química announced the addition of its brand to the club's uniform. Through an agreement valid until 2025, the company committed R\$ 20 million annually to feature its name on the central space of the team's jersey (UOL, 2021). Following these deals, various sectors of the stadium, previously known as North, South, East, and West, were rebranded with names of medications produced by Hypera Pharma, including Doril, Benegrip, Buscopan, Neosaldina, Epocler, and Engov sectors (Figure 22).

Figure 22: Multimillion-dollar sponsorships transformed the Corinthians team and stadium into a true "medicalizing billboard."

Source: NQA (2022). Elaborated by the author.

Hypera Pharma's extensive marketing efforts extend beyond its significant investment in Corinthians. For five consecutive years (2018-2022), the company has maintained a sponsorship deal with Rede Globo for football broadcasts, regarded as one of the priciest in Brazilian television. The latest renewal for 2022 cost the firm R\$ 307 million (Sacchitiello, 2021a), allowing it to market "Engov" and "Estomazil" during all football games aired by the network that year (Figure 23).

In 2022, Hypera Pharma also invested R\$ 11.8 million (Sacchitiello, 2021b) in sponsoring Brazil's most popular reality show, "Big Brother Brasil" (Rede Globo). For this venture, two segments of the program were named after the company's commercial medications (Figure 23). The "Engov After Party" was linked to the company's hangover medication, Engov, reflecting its use after events involving heavy alcohol consumption. Meanwhile, the tension-filled "Neosaldina bate e volta" challenge, which could lead to a contestant's elimination, was associated with Neosaldina, an analgesic for headaches and migraines. The packaging of these medications was even incorporated into the set design for these events.

Figure 23: Merchandising of Hypera Pharma's medications occupying central spaces in high-audience television programs in Brazil.

Source: Globo (2022); Hypera (2022). Elaborated by the author.

Hypera Pharma's substantial investment in Brazilian television advertising is strategic and has been yielding significant returns. The company has seen growth in several economic metrics, including sales to consumers, net profit, ongoing operations profit, and net revenue (Hypera, 2022). In 2022, Hypera Pharma reported a net profit of R\$ 1.33 billion, a 2.7% increase over the previous year (Carvalho; Rocha, 2022). Furthermore, it holds the highest revenue among pharmaceutical companies in Brazil, as detailed in "Table 3" of Chapter 1.

The examples cited reflect a broader, systematic trend of increasing investment in diverse advertising strategies and platforms by the pharmaceutical sector in Brazil. Data from the Kantar IBOPE database, part of the multinational "WPP Group" – one of the world's largest advertising organizations (Ibope, 2023) – shows a 176.9% increase in total investment for promoting pharmaceutical products on Brazilian television over a mere seven years (Figure 24). This surge propelled the pharmaceutical sector from 12th to 5th in the ranking of economic segments investing the most in television marketing in Brazil (Ibope, 2023).

Figure 24: Growth of the amount invested in television marketing by the pharmaceutical sector in Brazil (2012-2018).

Source: Ibope (2023). Elaborated by the author.

Beyond the collective investments of the sector depicted in Figure 24, individual pharmaceutical companies have also made significant outlays on their advertising campaigns. Data from Meio & Mensagem (M&M, 2022), as summarized in Table 7, reveals that over the last four years with available data (2017-2020), the pharmaceutical sector consistently placed three to four companies among Brazil's top ten advertisers. The advertising spend of some of these pharmaceutical companies even exceeded that of traditional Brazilian retail businesses, including beer and soft drink manufacturers, home appliance producers, as well as national financial institutions and telecommunications operators that serve thousands of cities and millions of users across the country.

Table 7: Pharmaceutical sector companies have a strong presence in the ranking of companies that invest the most in television marketing in Brazil (2017 - 2020).

2020			2019		
Ranking / Name		Millions (Reais - R\$)	Ranking / Name		Millions (Reais - R\$)
1°	Unilever	1,530	1°	Genomma Lab	848
2°	Genomma Lab	1,005	2°	Unilever	810
3°	Sky	888	3°	Vivo	420
4°	Bradesco	624	4°	Divcom Pharma	408
5°	Banco do Brasil	616	5°	Hypera Pharma	384
6°	Via Varejo	607	6°	Banco do Brasil	350
7°	Vivo	505	7°	Coca-Cola	315
8°	B2W	499	8°	Bradesco	312
9°	EMS	497	9°	Lojas Marabraz	306
10°	Hypera Pharma	476	10°	Claro	293
2018			2017		
Ranking / Name		Millions (Reais - R\$)	Ranking / Name		Millions (Reais - R\$)
1°	Genomma Lab	1,110	1°	Hypera Pharma	1,387
2°	Hypera Pharma	970	2°	Genomma Lab	1,156
3°	Unilever	506	3°	Unilever	657
4°	Ultrafarma	457	4°	Ambev	540
5°	Via Varejo	452	5°	Procter & Gamble	539
6°	Ambev	446	6°	Divcom Pharma	535
7°	Divcom Pharma	437	7°	Claro	504
8°	Claro	418	8°	Caixa	493
9°	Vivo	398	9°	Ultrafarma	469
10°	Caixa	378	10°	Via Varejo	444

 Pharmaceutical Sector Companies.

Source: M&M (2022). Elaborated by the author.

A thorough examination of the data over the period shown in the chart reveals that "Genomma Lab" and "Hypera Pharma" ranked first and third, respectively, in terms of marketing investment, cumulatively spending R\$ 7.3 billion over four years. Genomma Lab, originating from Mexico, allocated around R\$ 4.1 billion, claiming the top spot twice and securing the second position in two other years. Meanwhile, Hypera Pharma, leading in 2017, ranked second in 2018 and consistently stayed within the top ten in subsequent years. The Brazilian pharmaceutical company's total advertising expenditure during this period was approximately R\$ 3.2 billion. These figures strongly support the notion that the pharmaceutical

sector views drug advertising as an essential instrument for enhancing sales growth and profitability.

The pharmaceutical industry's success in drug production and commercialization has attracted attention from conglomerates and businesses in other economic sectors. A prime example is the American multinational "Procter & Gamble" (P&G), traditionally known for its expertise in personal hygiene and cleaning products. In response to the promising opportunities within the pharmaceutical sector, P&G has recently diversified, broadening its portfolio to include a range of medicines (Figure 25). This expansion encompasses anti-inflammatories, analgesics, herbal medicines, multivitamins, and supplements, illustrating the company's strategic foray into this lucrative market (P&G, 2022).

Figure 25: The conglomerate Procter & Gamble (P&G) expanded its activities to include the production and commercialization of various drugs.

Source: P&G (2022). Elaborated by the author.

Among the principal pharmaceutical offerings from Procter & Gamble (P&G), the well-known nasal decongestant "Vick" is prominent. This product recently broadened its range to encompass thirteen additional variants (P&G, 2022). In order to publicize these new introductions, P&G reinitiated its advertising campaigns across various national media platforms. The inaugural promotional campaign featured actor Lázaro Ramos and was prominently displayed during the reality show "Big Brother Brasil 22" (Vick, 2022).

During this period, P&G also sponsored the "leader's test" segment of the reality show, known for being one of the most viewed and costliest slots on Brazilian television (M&M, 2022). The setting of the test was adorned with displays of the brand's logo and its expanded product range. Both José Bonifácio Brasil, the director of the program, and Tadeu Schmidt, the host, took on roles akin to brand ambassadors (see Figure 26), further elevating the marketing initiative. This campaign extended beyond television, permeating the company's websites and social media platforms (Vick, 2022).

Figure 26: Multiscale promotions of the new Vick medication line.

Fonte: Globo (2022), Vick (2022). Elaborated by the author.

The rising profitability within the pharmaceutical sector has attracted the attention of major Brazilian retail giants, historically known for their presence in furniture, home appliances, and electronics domains. Retailers including "Casas Bahia," "Ponto," "Extra," "Americanas," and "Submarino" are now pivoting towards this burgeoning market, incorporating dedicated categories for "Health" or "Beauty and Health" on their online platforms (B2W, 2022; VIA, 2022).

Dietary supplements, which do not require medical prescriptions and have seen a consistent rise in demand within Brazil, are emerging as key products in this category (see Figure 27). The subcategories gaining particular prominence on these retail websites include multivitamins, probiotics, and essential fatty acids like omega-3. Additionally, supplements commonly used by amateur athletes and the elderly, such as Whey Protein, Creatine, BCAA, and Maltodextrin, are also gaining significant online visibility.

Figure 27: "Casas Bahia," a traditional Brazilian furniture and home appliance store, now offers over 152,000 purchase options related to "dietary supplements."

Source: VIA (2022). Elaborated by the author.

The expansive range of medicinal products available is largely attributed to an e-commerce innovation known as the "Marketplace." In this model, established companies, such as Casas Bahia, feature products from various sellers or firms on their websites. These host companies serve as intermediaries in transactions conducted via their portals, earning commissions based on sales volume or partnership fees from their commercial associates. This approach enables large corporations to diversify their product offerings, presenting a wider array of medicines and dietary supplements to consumers.

Accompanying this variety, these companies often provide marketing incentives and discounts linked to bulk purchasing options (refer to Figure 27). Such schemes allow consumers to avail discounts when buying products in large quantities or multiple units. Another prevalent strategy is "tied selling," wherein the system recommends discounts or promotions on additional medications when a customer makes a specific purchase. However, these practices

have sparked concerns, as they might inadvertently promote an unnecessary increase in drug consumption.

Internet, Artificial Intelligence, and the Revolution in Qualitative Pharmaceutical Marketing

The advancements in computing and internet technologies, particularly artificial intelligence, have not only expanded quantitatively but also enhanced qualitative marketing. This progression has led to marketing strategies that are more personalized, specific, and accurate. In a manner akin to how audiences of radio and television were invariably exposed to numerous advertisements, the internet today is similarly inundated with an array of strategically designed and programmed advertisements aimed at reaching specific consumers.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) algorithms function as sophisticated tools, analyzing and correlating vast volumes of data more precisely than human capabilities. Every internet action - from searches in search engines, clicks on news headlines, views on entertainment channels, interactions on social networks, to visits to online store pages - is meticulously tracked. As internet usage increases, so does the accuracy and computational analysis in identifying our preference patterns, thereby suggesting content, products, and services that resonate with our consumption trends.

In this technologically driven era, where internet connectivity is increasingly pervasive, "digital pharmaceutical marketing" has become a significant part of our daily lives. Simple online activities, such as searching for symptoms like a headache on search engines or watching videos about such symptoms, can lead to targeted drug advertisements in the days following on various platforms like social networks, news sites, and music platforms.

Furthermore, the qualitative leap in algorithms and artificial intelligence has enabled targeted drug advertising based on various factors, including age group, gender, economic status, educational level, and geographic location. For example, data from social networks can be used to tailor advertisements, such as directing ads for menstrual cramp relief to women, painkillers to young professionals, flu syrups to mothers with young children, sexual enhancers to middle-aged men, vitamin supplements to the elderly, and so on.

Figure 28: Pharmaceutical advertisements intensify across various online platforms.

Source: Globo (2022); Instagram (2022). Elaborated by the author.

The expansion and diversification of social networks have significantly widened the scope of visibility and have led to the rise of a new breed of "internet personalities" - digital influencers, bloggers, and YouTubers. These individuals, often compensated for content promotion, wield considerable influence over consumer behavior, swaying their followers towards specific products. This phenomenon is especially notable in Brazil, a nation with one of the highest levels of social media engagement. Statistically, Brazil holds the fifth-largest number of active social media users globally, amounting to 165.5 million (Statista, 2023), and it ranks second in terms of average daily usage, with users spending about 3 hours and 42 minutes daily on social media, translating to roughly 56 days per year (Sortlist, 2022).

In the pharmaceutical industry, this novel form of online merchandising has empowered various internet celebrities to earn compensation for promoting pharmaceutical companies and their products. These influencers often highlight the benefits of certain medications, presenting themselves as satisfied users of these drugs. This marketing tactic not only benefits the

pharmaceutical companies by broadening their reach but also significantly shapes the perceptions and choices of their followers in regard to these medical products.

Figure 29: Marta Silva, a player for the Brazilian national football team, and Rodrigo Hilbert, an actor and presenter, promoting pharmaceutical companies on their personal Instagram accounts, where they collectively have 7.1 million followers.

Source: Instagram (2022). Elaborated by the author.

The strategy of leveraging internet personalities for pharmaceutical marketing is not unique to Brazil but is prevalent in other countries as well. A notable case involved American influencer and socialite Kim Kardashian, one of the top personalities on Instagram in terms of followers. In August 2015, she faced repercussions for a social media post promoting a morning sickness medication from Canadian pharmaceutical company Duchesnay while she was pregnant. The U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) criticized the post for being misleading, as it highlighted the drug's effectiveness without mentioning associated risks and failed to state that it was not recommended for women sensitive to specific drugs. At that time, Kim Kardashian had approximately 42 million Instagram followers and 34 million Twitter followers.

In Brazil, an illustrative example is "Growth Supplements," a company specializing in supplements, which sponsors 53 advertising partners, including athletes, bloggers, YouTubers, and influencers. These partners use their social media platforms to promote the company's products to their followers. Collectively, the "Team Growth" personalities boast a significant social media presence, with a total of 21.7 million followers on Instagram and 15.4 million on YouTube, illustrating the expansive reach and influence of this marketing strategy in today's digital landscape.

Figure 30: Growth Supplements has a "team" of 53 advertising partners composed of various internet personalities.

Source: Growth (2022). Elaborated by the author.

The surge in internet access and accompanying cultural shifts have led to a novel form of direct communication between companies and consumers. Through an array of digital platforms like social networks, video sharing sites, websites, and blogs, companies are increasingly investing in creating advertisements that blend seamlessly with news, entertaining content, motivational messages, and other varied content types. This strategy aims to captivate and retain customers by offering them more than just conventional advertisements.

A case in point is the YouTube channel 'Growth TV,' operated by Growth Supplements. This channel invites internet users to engage with a range of content covering training, nutrition, health, humor, and entertainment. With a subscriber base of 2.1 million, Growth TV has garnered over 300 million views across its extensive library of videos, all available for free viewing. In addition to YouTube, Growth Supplements has a significant presence on other social media platforms. They maintain an Instagram page with 1.4 million followers, a Facebook page with 616.7 thousand followers, and also run a blog and a website. These platforms are not only

channels for disseminating information but also serve as tools for customer engagement and sales, exemplifying the integration of content creation and marketing in the digital era.

Figure 31: The promotional and engagement page of Growth Supplements on Instagram has 1.4 million followers.

Source: Growth (2022); Instagram (2022). Elaborated by the author.

The data and analysis presented underscore the significant and escalating impact of online advertising in today's digital landscape. This environment presents a multifaceted market scenario characterized by substantial financial transactions and a broad sphere of influence. The tendencies for excess, once predominantly associated with traditional media such as radio and television, appear to have intensified in the highly fragmented realm of the internet. This issue

is particularly pressing in sectors like the pharmaceutical industry, where the stakes involve both public and individual health concerns.

Additionally, many collaborations between companies and digital influencers are often forged informally, leaving the public unaware of the financial incentives or other benefits attached to the content being promoted. This lack of transparency puts internet users at a disadvantage, as they may not be able to discern the true motivations behind the endorsement of a particular medication or pharmaceutical company. Consequently, consumers may find it challenging to differentiate between genuine recommendations and those driven by undisclosed commercial interests, raising concerns about the ethical implications of such marketing practices in the digital age.

The Distortion Between Brazilian Advertising Legislation and Its Application

The examination of historical patterns, supported by empirical data and case studies addressed earlier, underscores the potential dangers associated with pharmaceutical advertising. This includes the dissemination of misleading or, occasionally, outright inaccurate information, along with a surplus of marketing materials focused predominantly on boosting sales and profits, which may jeopardize public health. Considering the State's ethical and political duty to safeguard citizens from detrimental influences (Vasconcellos; Machado, 2011; Vasconcellos; Gaze, 2013), it becomes a primary responsibility of the State to oversee and regulate such activities.

The roots of pharmaceutical advertising regulation in Brazil can be traced back to the 1930s. Getúlio Vargas, intent on modernizing the nation, initiated the establishment of the "Ministry of Education and Public Health Affairs" (Brazil, 1930) at the start of his administration, appointing the legal expert Francisco de Campos as its head. Within ten months, in September 1931, Vargas, collaborating with Belisário Augusto de Oliveira Penna, a public health physician and the successor to Francisco de Campos, in the now rebranded "Ministry of State for Education and Public Health," promulgated Decree No. 20,377 (Brazil, 1931). This decree, a pioneering step, governed the pharmaceutical profession in Brazil and laid down the inaugural legal structure for controlling pharmaceutical advertising in the country (Thielen; Santos, 2002). Of the 180 articles proposed in this decree, it was defined:

Article 112: It is strictly prohibited to **advertise**, sell, manufacture, or manipulate secret preparations and to attribute to licensed products curative or hygienic properties that have not been mentioned in the respective license by the National Department of Public Health.

Article 122: **Advertisements** for pharmaceutical specialties, outside of scientific journals and technical publications, shall be limited exclusively to the terms of the license granted by the National Department of Public Health.

Article 123: It is expressly forbidden to **advertise** pharmaceutical specialties through their therapeutic indications, with insinuations of responses via post office boxes, institutes, residences, and other means (Brazil, 1931).

In subsequent decades, particularly throughout the 1970s, the evolution of marketing tactics, propelled by television's emergence as the dominant communication medium in Brazil, rendered the existing laws outdated and often overlooked (Araújo *et al.*, 2012). This situation was aggravated by the absence of dedicated oversight bodies to monitor and penalize companies infringing upon legal standards. It was against this backdrop that the National Health Surveillance Secretariat (SNVA) was founded in 1976, tasked with, among other responsibilities, ensuring adherence to health regulations and standards concerning medical and pharmaceutical products across Brazil (Brazil, 1976). The ensuing year saw the implementation of new regulations, banning the broadcast of prescription drug advertisements to the general public and prohibiting the use of illustrations or decorations on medication labels and leaflets (Brazil, 1977).

For the physician and researcher Luiz Carlos Fadel de Vasconcellos (Oswaldo Cruz Foundation), the implementation of the Unified Health System (SUS) (Castro *et al.*, 2019) through the Federal Constitution of 1988 and the subsequent creation of the National Health Surveillance Agency (Anvisa) in 1999 marked important stages in the progression of supervision and improvement of public health in Brazil (Faleiros *et al.*, 2006; Vasconcellos, 2007; Gomez *et al.*, 2018). Now, it is the responsibility of Anvisa to regulate, control, and inspect products and services that may pose risks to public health, including human-use medicines, as well as their active substances, other inputs, processes, and technologies (Brazil, 1999).

In 2008, a pivotal development occurred with the publication of "Resolution-RDC No. 96," which revised the laws concerning "advertising, publicity, information, and other practices related to the dissemination or commercial promotion of medicines" (Brazil, 2008). This resolution emerged as the primary regulatory framework for pharmaceutical advertising in Brazil.

Nevertheless, despite these significant legislative improvements, the practical application in terms of enforcement and penalization is still markedly inadequate (Nascimento; Sayd, 2005; Fagundes *et al.*, 2007; Soares, 2008; Nascimento, 2009; Araújo *et al.*, 2012). This shortfall contributes to the ongoing instances of non-compliance and threats to public health, manifested in abusive and deceptive drug advertisements, as highlighted in this chapter. Such issues persist nearly a century after the initial regulatory efforts initiated during the Vargas era in 1930.

Álvaro César Nascimento, a scholar at the Department of Social Sciences of the National School of Public Health (ENSP/Fiocruz) and an author of various studies on drug advertising in Brazil, posits that the regulation of pharmaceutical advertising remains weak and fraught with inconsistencies (Nascimento, 2007; 2009; 2010). Typically, when regulatory actions are taken, they occur post-violation, by which time the public has already been subjected to potential health hazards. The penalties levied are trivial compared to the companies' profits and advertising expenditures. Furthermore, the common advisory - "If symptoms persist, consult a doctor" - inadvertently promotes self-medication by suggesting medical consultation only if symptoms continue following medication use (Nascimento, 2009).

The "MonitorAÇÃO Project," a collaborative effort between the Federal Fluminense University (UFF) and the National Health Surveillance Agency (Anvisa), along with eighteen universities throughout Brazil, undertook an extensive study of drug advertising in the nation. Between October 2004 and August 2005, the project documented 263 instances of advertising irregularities, as noted by Soares (2008), a Public Health expert and one of the project's leaders.

These advertisements, distributed across various platforms such as medical offices, pharmacies, specialized journals, and radio and television programs, displayed numerous inconsistencies. The most notable issues included the omission of essential information, presentation of misleading data, promotion of unregistered drugs, lack of mention of contraindications for the advertised products and the excessive encouragement of uncontrolled medication use, especially for drugs requiring a prescription (Soares, 2008).

The insights and evaluations presented in this chapter lead to a contemplation of how the present manner of drug advertising – characterized by exaggeration and distortion – clashes with the prudent use of pharmaceuticals. Such advertising approaches contribute to higher drug prices and foster the practice of self-medication. By downplaying discussions about potential adverse effects, there is a marked focus on spurring consumption rather than providing essential information, often supplanting the role of healthcare professionals. This shift burdens citizens

and the State (Vasconcellos, 2007) with the financial, individual, and collective health repercussions (Vasconcellos; Gaze, 2013) associated with potential complications or conditions exacerbated by irrational medication use.

Several experts, like Nascimento (2009) and Araújo *et al.* (2012), suggest transitioning to a model of pre-analysis and approval for drug advertisements in Brazil, a strategy already in place in other regions. To appreciate the significance of this proposal, it's instructive to consider the regulation of cigarette advertising in Brazil. Despite being a product known for its detrimental effects on individual and collective health, the regulation of cigarette advertising only commenced in 1996, initially limiting advertisements to nighttime hours (Brazil, 1996). Later, in 2000, these restrictions were extended (Brazil, 2000), culminating in 2011 with the complete prohibition of cigarette advertising in the country (Brazil, 2011).

This delayed but important progress marked the termination of exploiting legislative loopholes and lobbying efforts by major international corporations with the Brazilian government (Cavalcante, 2005). Comparable to the current situation with medications, these corporations had heavily invested in compelling marketing techniques to portray cigarettes and smoking as symbols of virility, glamour, and modernity throughout the 20th century, only to later confront significant societal and state-level harm.

CONCLUSIONS

Conclusions

The comprehensive investigation in this study, drawing on various sources, authors, and global data, corroborates the assertion that the pharmaceutical companies have become a dominant and influential force in the global economy. Our analysis shed light on multiple factors fueling this rise, including diversified drug portfolios, enhanced production capabilities, and escalating demand for pharmaceuticals. The industry's complex strategies, often perceived as distortions, biases, or excesses, were highlighted. These include substantial lobbying efforts and political funding, influence over regulatory agencies, ties with patient groups, impacts on clinical guideline development, and manipulation in drug research and marketing. Additionally, the study noted the industry's financial entanglements with health professionals and consumer-targeted marketing tactics, frequently misleading.

Since Alexander Fleming's discovery of penicillin in 1928, the pharmaceutical industry has transformed dramatically. Firms have evolved from small, often family-run operations focused on local or regional markets into multinational corporations with immense global reach and valuations in the hundreds of billions of dollars.

In the past two decades, the industry has seen remarkable growth. Its annual revenue nearly quadrupled, reaching an astounding \$1.48 trillion, comparable to the GDP of major economies like Spain. Today, the industry is characterized by an oligopolistic landscape, dominated by the top twenty companies, mainly based in the U.S. and Europe, with a combined market value of \$3.5 trillion. These companies hold assets worth \$1.86 trillion and have achieved \$820 billion in revenues, leading to profits of about \$181.6 billion. The sector's dynamism is further evidenced by its 784 merger and acquisition deals in 2022, totaling \$126 billion.

These figures underscore the tremendous power and influence of the pharmaceutical companies. The assets of just the top twenty companies equal the GDP of the forty-eight countries in Sub-Saharan Africa. On an individual scale, companies like Johnson & Johnson, with a market value of \$477.4 billion, surpass the GDP of 184 countries.

To counterbalance the dominance of North American and European pharmaceutical firms, a cohort of companies from "pharmerging" nations, primarily in Asia, is gaining prominence and competitiveness on the global stage. The Chinese pharmaceutical industry, for example, has seen remarkable growth, now comprising about 5,000 companies. Nine of these rank among the world's 44 largest pharmaceutical firms. China has also markedly increased its new drug development, escalating from 95 in 2007 to 3,100 in 2021, and has become the world's

leading producer of Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients (APIs).

India, another emerging powerhouse in Asia, is home to over 3,000 pharmaceutical companies and around 10,500 manufacturing units. Specializing in affordable generic drugs, primarily for middle and low-income nations, Indian firms now produce more than 60,000 brands across over sixty therapeutic categories.

Despite a global increase in medicine accessibility, availability remains disproportionately higher in developed countries. The United States and Canada together account for nearly half (49.1%) of global pharmaceutical spending, followed by Europe (23.3%) and Japan (6.1%). Among emerging markets, only China has a significant share, holding 9.4% of the global market.

However, the demand for pharmaceutical products in emerging countries, especially in Asia and Latin America, is rising rapidly. This surge is propelled by nations like Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa (BRICS), along with Mexico, Indonesia, South Korea, and Turkey (MIST). These nine nations, experiencing notable economic growth, represent 48% of the global population and 31% of the world's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). This scenario presents a substantial opportunity for increased sales for established pharmaceutical companies and the emergence of new regional or local players.

Investments in Research and Development (R&D) within the pharmaceutical sector mirror its growth, escalating to \$238 billion in 2021, a 74% increase from 2012. Over the last two decades, there has been a 4.5-fold increase in the number of companies engaged in new drug development, now exceeding 5,400 organizations. Presently, around 20,000 drugs are at various stages of the R&D pipeline.

However, despite this substantial volume, a majority of the newly approved drugs do not offer significant improvements over existing treatments. Many of these "new" drugs are actually (re)formulations or combinations of older medications. This tactic is often employed to prolong the commercial viability of drugs nearing the end of their patent life or to penetrate markets dominated by rivals. This strategy also mitigates the financial risks associated with R&D, fostering safer and more consistent profits for the companies.

Moreover, there's a discernible bias and neglect in investment for new drug research. Pharmaceutical companies predominantly focus their R&D on diseases with the widest population impact, such as chronic and infectious diseases, and complex conditions like cancer, seeking greater financial returns. However, other comorbidities, particularly those affecting low-income populations in developing countries, are often overlooked. This "neglect" translates

into insufficient R&D investment, leading to high mortality rates in various parts of the world.

The data and analyses underscore a fierce competition within the pharmaceutical sector, especially among the United States, China, and the European Union. This rivalry is evident in various aspects, such as the dominance of the largest companies, the division of global market share, and the approval rate of new chemical and biological entities. This competitive landscape mirrors broader geopolitical dynamics already apparent in other socioeconomic areas. These three players combined account for approximately 60% of the total global economic output, valued at \$96.5 trillion. This statistic highlights their significant influence that extends well beyond the pharmaceutical industry, underscoring their global economic prowess.

While pharmaceutical companies have risen as major players in the global economy, they are also engaged in a relentless quest for power, capital, and influence. This pursuit often skirts ethical boundaries, potentially jeopardizing patient welfare and public health. A notable instance of this is the substantial investment in lobbying and electoral funding. In the United States, the pharmaceutical sector leads in lobbying expenditures, outspending the second-ranked industry by 60%. From 1998 to 2022, pharmaceutical and health product companies poured \$5.4 billion into lobbying activities in the U.S.

The number of lobbyists for the pharmaceutical and health product industries has steadily increased, climbing from 747 in 1998 to 1,840 in 2022. About 65% of these lobbyists, representing pharmaceutical interests in the U.S., are former government officials, including ex-regulators, public servants, and former Congress members. They are attracted by the financial and influential clout of these corporations. Furthermore, the sector has made multi-billion-dollar contributions to the electoral campaigns of a wide range of candidates, from presidential contenders to governors, senators, and federal and state legislators.

The pharmaceutical industry's influence extends to regulatory and supervisory bodies, patient organizations, and the development of Clinical Guidelines. The industry's financing has strengthened its control over "Advisory Committees" involved in drug market decisions. In roughly 73% of these committees' meetings, tied to the Food and Drug Administration (FDA), at least one member disclosed a conflict of interest, sometimes involving substantial sums. These conflicted members often played crucial roles in decisions about controversial drugs, such as the anti-inflammatory Vioxx (rofecoxib), despite evidence of associated health risks.

Patient organizations, meant to promote public policies and foster research and debate, have been co-opted through funding that runs into millions annually. Many include pharmaceutical executives on their boards, enabling industry-biased stances on issues like drug

pricing and generic drug prohibition. Additionally, a significant number of Clinical Guidelines authors, whose work influences global medication use, are sponsored by pharmaceutical companies, raising concerns about potential biases in these influential documents.

The pharmaceutical industry's financial might has made it the primary funder of drug trials worldwide, leading to intricate and potentially problematic ties with researchers and academic institutions. This influence raises concerns about the integrity of the scientific method. One illustrative case is that of Seroquel (quetiapine), marketed by AstraZeneca. Legal documents exposed the company's manipulation of studies to overstate Seroquel's benefits in treating schizophrenia, despite its inferior efficacy, to safeguard its high sales exceeding \$5 billion annually. This strategy contributed to Seroquel's financial success, generating \$36.7 billion for AstraZeneca between 1999 and 2011, until the drug's exclusive marketing patent expired.

Pharmaceutical companies also actively engage with healthcare professionals, particularly doctors, through extensive funding and gifts. In the United States, between 2015 and 2021, these companies spent \$14.78 billion on various incentives for doctors, including gifts, meals, travel, accommodations, education, entertainment, consulting fees, payments for educational or speaking roles, and other items.

Similarly, around \$14.59 billion was directed to university hospitals in the U.S. during the same period. These funds primarily supported research, events, meals, educational materials, and more. However, some drugs associated with these financial transactions, such as the anticoagulant Xarelto (rivaroxaban), later became subject to lawsuits. In the case of Xarelto, the litigation centered on failure to warn patients about risks of fatal bleeding linked to its use.

Despite drugs being distinct from typical consumer goods, pharmaceutical companies heavily invest in direct-to-consumer marketing to boost sales and profits. In Brazil, the pharmaceutical industry is among the top investors in marketing, with several companies leading in individual advertising expenditures.

Historical analyses of pharmaceutical marketing in Brazil reveal instances of misleading advertising, similar to trends observed globally. Examples include promoting harmful substances like cocaine as remedies for common ailments and advertising beers as treatments for anemia in women and children.

In the past, posters, leaflets, radio, and newspapers were the primary channels for pharmaceutical advertising. However, today, television and the internet dominate. From 2012 to 2018, investment in pharmaceutical product advertising on Brazilian television surged by

176.9%. In the most recent data (2017-2020), three to four pharmaceutical companies consistently ranked among Brazil's top ten advertisers, outspending traditional retail sectors and national institutions.

The rise of the internet and technologies like algorithms and artificial intelligence (AI) has transformed pharmaceutical marketing. For instance, a simple online search for symptoms can result in targeted medication advertisements on social media, news sites, and other platforms in the following days. Furthermore, the use of celebrities as digital influencers to endorse medications is increasingly common, often portraying them as successful product users.

However, despite Brazil having legal frameworks to regulate pharmaceutical marketing, there is a notable lack of effective supervision and enforcement. This leniency leads to the perception that violations are beneficial and carry minimal repercussions for the offending pharmaceutical companies.

The numbers, discoveries, and insights discussed underscore the complexity of the pharmaceutical sector, the influence of its leading companies, and the often questionable business practices employed in the quest to increase sales and maximize profits, sometimes at the cost of public health and collective well-being.

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ANNEXES

Annex 1: Market Value, Assets, Sales, and Profit of the 44 Largest Pharmaceutical Companies in the World in 2022.

Ranking / Name	Country	Values in Billion Dollars (USD)				
		Market Value	Assets	Revenues	Profit	
1	Johnson & Johnson	United States	477.4	182.0	94.9	19.83
2	Roche holding	Switzerland	308.1	101.3	68.7	15.24
3	AbbVie	United States	273.8	146.5	56.2	11.46
4	Pfizer	United States	271.8	181.5	81.5	21.98
5	Eli Lilly	United States	265.5	48.8	28.3	5.58
6	Novo Nordisk	Denmark	252.9	29.7	22.4	7.59
7	Merck & Co.	United States	213.8	105.7	50.4	13.05
8	AstraZeneca	United Kingdom	204.6	105.4	38.7	0.09
9	Novartis	Switzerland	200.7	135.9	51.6	24.14
10	Bristol Myers Squibb	United States	161.0	109.3	46.4	6.99
11	Sanofi	France	136.9	136.7	44.6	7.36
12	Amgen	United States	133.6	61.2	26.0	5.89
13	GlaxoSmithKline	United Kingdom	112.1	107.1	46.9	6.03
14	CSL	Australia	94.7	23.4	10.6	2.36
15	Gilead Sciences	United States	78.2	68.0	27.4	6.22
16	Regeneron Pharmaceuticals	United States	74.7	25.4	16.1	8.08
17	Bayer	Germany	70.1	144.2	52.1	1.18
18	Vertex Pharmaceuticals	United States	68.8	13.4	7.6	2.34
19	Moderna	United States	56.6	24.9	18.4	12.20
20	Takeda Pharmaceutical	Japan	45.3	110.3	31.6	3.99
21	Daiichi Sankyo	Japan	43.9	18.8	9.4	0.86
22	Jiangsu Hengrui Medicine	China	32.3	6.0	4.4	0.96
23	Biogen	United States	30.9	23.9	10.4	1.56
24	WuXi Biologics	China	30.2	6.9	1.6	0.53
25	Astellas Pharma	Japan	29.3	20.5	11.8	1.09
26	Sun Pharma Industries	India	29.0	9.3	5.1	0.87
27	Zhangzhou Pientzhuang	China	27.5	2.0	1.2	0.38
28	West Pharmaceutical Services	United States	26.0	3.3	2.8	0.66
29	Chongqing Zhifei Biological	China	25.2	4.7	4.7	1.58
30	UCB	Belgium	22.4	16.2	6.8	1.25
31	Royalty Pharma	United States	18.5	17.5	2.3	0.62
32	Otsuka Holding	Japan	17.9	24.5	13.6	1.14
33	Shionogi	Japan	16.3	9.0	2.7	0.88

34	CSPC Pharmaceutical Group	Hong Kong	12.5	5.5	4.3	0.87
35	Viartis	United States	12.4	54.8	17.9	-1.27
36	Grifols	Spain	11.9	22.0	5.8	0.22
37	Teva Pharmaceutical	Israel	10.6	47.7	15.9	0.42
38	Shanghai Fosun Pharmaceutical	China	10.2	14.6	6.0	0.73
39	Sino Biopharmaceutical	Hong Kong	9.6	8.7	3.8	1.54
40	Sinopharm Group	China	6.8	52.6	80.8	1.20
41	Shanghai Pharmaceuticals	China	6.0	25.6	33.4	0.79
42	Jointown Pharmaceutical Group	China	3.7	13.4	18.8	0.51
43	China Resources Pharmaceutical	Hong Kong	3.2	31.9	30.5	0.48
44	Hubei Biocause Pharmaceutical	China	2.4	39.1	6.5	0.05
Total		-	3,939.0	2,339.3	1,120.8	199.5

Source: Forbes (2023). Elaborated by the author.

Annex 2: The Group of Nine Emerging Countries, Including BRICS and MIST, Accounts for 48% of the World Population and 31% of the Global Economy (GDP).

(BRICS)	GDP (Million USD)	Population
Brasil	1,608,981.46	218,505,624
Russia	1,778,782.63	146,109,129
Índia	3,176,295.07	1,433,583,102
China	17,734,062.65	1,462,197,912
África do Sul	419,015.02	61,153,879
(MIST)	GDP (Million USD)	Population
México	1,272,839.33	134,389,201
Indonésia	1,186,092.99	284,220,007
Coreia, Rep.	1,810,955.87	52,104,606
Turquia	819,035.18	88,842,891
Total	29,806,060.20	3,881,106,351

Source: WB (2023). Elaborated by the author.

Annex 3: Between 2001 and 2022, the Total Size of the Global Pharmaceutical Research and Development (R&D) Pipeline Increased by 3.4 Times.

Source: Citeline (2022). Elaborated by the author.

Annex 4: The Group of 25 Companies with the Highest Number of Substances in Development Accounts for Over 3,000 Drugs.

Posição	Nome	Nº de Drogas no Pipeline
1	Novartis	213
2	Roche	200
3	Takeda	184
4	Bristol Myers Squibb	168
5	Pfizer	168
6	AstraZeneca	161
7	Merck & Co	158
8	Johnson & Johnson	157
9	Sanofi	151
10	Eli Lilly	142
11	GlaxoSmithKline	131
12	AbbVie	121
13	Boehringer Ingelheim	108
14	Bayer	105
15	Otsuka Holdings	93
16	Jiangsu Hengrui Pharmaceuticals	89
17	Amgen	83
18	Eisai	80
19	Astellas Pharma	75
20	Daiichi Sankyo	75
21	Gilead Sciences	72
22	Regeneron	68
23	Shanghai Fosun Pharmaceutical	68
24	Biogen	66
25	Sumitomo Dainippon Pharma	66
Total		3,002

Source: Citeline (2022). Elaborated by the author.

Annex 5: The United States (24.2%), China (18.4%), and the European Union (17.8%) Account for 60.4% of the Global Economy (GDP) in 2021.

Source: WB (2023). Elaborated by the author.

Additional Table: Countries with GDP Over \$1 Trillion and Their Percentage of the Global Economy (2021).

Country	GDP (Trillions USD)	(%)
United States	23.315	24.2
China	17.734	18.4
European Union	17.177	17.8
Japan	4.941	5.1
India	3.176	3.3
United Kingdom	3.131	3.2
South Korea	1.811	1.9
Russia	1.779	1.8
Brazil	1.609	1.7
Australia	1.553	1.6
Mexico	1.273	1.3
Indonesia	1.186	1.2
Other Countries	17.842	18.4
Global Total	96.527	100,0

Source: WB (2023). Elaborated by the author.

Annex 6: Distribution of Sales by Drug Category in the Brazilian Retail Market in 2022.

Category	Revenue (Millions of Brazilian Reais)	Percentage Distribution	Sales (Millions of Boxes)	Percentage Distribution	Average Price (BRL)
Generic	15,364.5	14.4%	1.892,5	35.4%	8,1
Branded and Similar	54,033.9	50.6%	2.600,8	48.7%	20,8
Reference	37,386.7	35.0%	848,8	15.9%	44,0
Total	106.785,1	100.00%	5.342,1	100.00%	19,9

Source: Sindusfarma (2023). Elaborated by the author.

Annex 7: Deficit in the Brazilian Pharmaceutical Sector's Trade Balance Reached \$6.387 Billion (Negative) in 2022.

Source: Sindusfarma (2023). Elaborated by the author.

Annex 8: Annual Lobbying Investments Made by the “Pharmaceutical and Health Products Industry” in the United States (1998-2022).

Year	Total Amount (USD)
1998	69,618,254
1999	84,804,372
2000	100,055,942
2001	100,564,597
2002	120,549,798
2003	129,992,469
2004	147,340,240
2005	167,886,306
2006	187,572,247
2007	229,042,258
2008	240,775,163
2009	275,439,217
2010	248,261,620
2011	243,441,907
2012	237,127,949
2013	229,046,434
2014	230,758,439
2015	242,137,411
2016	248,504,189
2017	278,643,442
2018	285,537,644
2019	302,811,612
2020	317,138,801
2021	362,304,789
2022	373,743,282
Total	5,453,098,382

Source: OpenSecrets (2023). Elaborated by the author.

Annex 9: Donations from the “Pharmaceutical and Health Products Industry” to Congressional (and Presidential) Election Campaigns in the United States between 1990 and 2020.

Year	Total Amount (USD)	
	Congressional	Presidential*
1990	3,061,509	
1992	4,747,089	
1994	5,197,190	
1996	6,419,743	
1998	6,136,274	
2000	9,919,282	
2002	9,550,104	
2004	14,970,282	
2006	17,609,414	
2008	25,527,264	5,075,153
2010	22,762,491	
2012	29,481,405	4,356,578
2014	23,020,264	
2016	31,890,659	16,906,448
2018	30,217,406	
2020	52,035,559	24,663,506
Total	292,545,935	51,001,685

Source: OpenSecrets (2023). Elaborated by the author.

* Data available only for the last four presidential elections.

Annex 10: With \$196.3 Billion in Revenue, Humira (Adalimumab) Accounted for 49.9% of All AbbVie Pharmaceutical's Earnings During the 2010/22 Period.

Source: AbbVie (2023). Elaborated by the author.

Annex 11: Baseball Player Rafael Palmeiro, then 37 years old and playing for the Texas Rangers, in a Campaign as a Viagra User in 2002.

I TAKE BATTING PRACTICE | Over 450 home runs

I TAKE INFIELD PRACTICE | 3 Gold Gloves

I TAKE VIAGRA | Let's just say it works for me

Like Rafael Palmeiro, VIAGRA has some impressive stats. In 4 years, more than 44 million prescriptions have been written in the United States alone. Plus, VIAGRA has helped more than 13 million men worldwide rediscover their love lives. Hey, it all adds up. So do what Rafael did. Ask your doctor if a free sample of VIAGRA is right for you.

VIAGRA® (sildenafil citrate) tablets PROUD SPONSOR

For more information, visit www.viagra.com

Please see patient summary of information for VIAGRA (25-mg, 50-mg, 100-mg) tablets on the following page.

VIAGRA is indicated for the treatment of erectile dysfunction. Remember that no medicine is for everyone. If you use nitrate drugs, often used to control chest pain (also known as angina), don't take VIAGRA. This combination could cause your blood pressure to drop to an unsafe or life-threatening level. Discuss your general health status with your doctor to ensure that you are healthy enough to engage in sexual activity. If you experience chest pain, nausea, or any other discomforts during sex or an erection that lasts longer than 4 hours, seek immediate medical help. The most common side effects of VIAGRA are headache, facial flushing, and upset stomach. Less commonly, bluish vision, blurred vision, or sensitivity to light may briefly occur.

Source: Brisbee (2014).

Annex 12: Pfizer Employs Young Celebrities in its Commercials to Promote Viagra (Sildenafil), a Medication for the Treatment of Male Erectile Dysfunction.

Description	Link	Language
Viagra Commercials, Featuring Three-Time World Cup Champion, Football Player Pelé (Edson Arantes do Nascimento).	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iXKAUU8dYxw	Portuguese (Brazil)
	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=T1s2nhTu3L4	Spanish
Rafael Palmeiro, a 37-year-old baseball player and member of the Texas Rangers in 2002, stars in commercials where he identifies as a user of the medication, linking it to the masculinity and virility traditionally associated with baseball.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ci5oenGU-mw	English
	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1-vTJIFUjmY	English

Source: Youtube (2023). Elaborated by the author.

Annex 13: Paxil (Paroxetine) Advertisements Filled with Alarmist Messages.

Description	Link	Language
<p>Appealing advertisements broadcast on a national scale depicted social phobia and social anxiety as debilitating conditions affecting a vast number of people. Phrases like "over 10 million Americans suffer from social anxiety," "imagine being allergic to people," "do you suffer?", "Paxil offers new hope," "Paxil helps correct the chemical imbalance associated with this disorder," incited the public to try Paxil, promising an encouraging outcome as hinted in the advertising.</p>	<p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=O_v3bIVpWSg</p>	<p>English</p>
	<p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dQmNOx-gBPM</p>	<p>English</p>

Source: Youtube (2023). Elaborated by the author.

Annex 14: Cimed's Advertising Campaign Hired "Tite", the Coach of the Brazilian National Football Team, During the 2018 World Cup.

Source: Cimed (2022). Elaborated by the author.